

Sketched Smiles: Performers and Comic Repertoire at the Paris Opéra under the reign of Louis XIV

Lola Salem
Oriel College, Oxford

The founding document of the Académie Royale de Musique (ARM), a royal decree (*lettres patentes*) given in 1669 to Pierre Perrin and renewed in 1672 in favour of Jean-Baptiste Lully, does not provide substantial details about the repertoire desired for production. Rather, it emphasises the need to establish a French counterpart to the opera houses based in “Italy, Germany, and England”.¹ Even projected costs for “stages, machines, decors, costumes, and other necessary things” remain unspecified.² Likewise, the entry “opera” in Antoine Furetière’s 1690 *Dictionnaire* remains quiet about the tone, shapes and contours of the plots and their musical adaptations, despite echoing the importance of visual splendour in opera production already mentioned in the ARM’s founding document.³

Yet, whether in terms of institutional structure and artistic content, the ARM drew from different pre-existing models since its inception. With regard to genres and performance practices, Italian opera—which Mazarin imported to the French court between 1645 and 1662—and French spoken theatre were two obvious points of comparison for contemporaries. Seventeenth- and eighteenth-century intellectual discussions addressing these topics traditionally interlocked with elements of literary criticism. Critics inquired about the origins of performance arts (including, traditionally, a commentary on Ancient Greek sources and projected practices), and dealt with the nature and aims of contemporary theatrical principles. French classical (spoken) theatre was grounded in a set of unity rules—place, time, action, and verisimilitude—whose definitions and applications were subjects of extensive debate. Nicolas Boileau’s *Art poétique* (published in 1674, the same year as *Alceste* by Jean-Baptiste Lully and Philippe Quinault) is a quintessential example of this tradition. Its paradigmatic influence over his generation and subsequent ones established a robust model, summarised as the “Boileau effect” by literary theorist Sima Godfrey.⁴ This influence remains central in many contemporary intellectual circles.

In seventeenth-century France, nearly every decade faced a “moral crisis” related to theatre, significantly affecting the issue of “comedy” on stage and its inclusion in the repertoire.⁵

¹“Lettres patentes”, F-Pan, O1/16, 13 March 1672.

²Idem: “pour les théâtres, machines, décorations, habits, qu’autres choses nécessaires”.

³Antoine Furetière, *Dictionnaire universel* (La Haye and Rotterdam, 1690), s.v. “Opéra”: “Spectacle public, représentation magnifique sur la scène, de quelque ouvrage dramatique, dont les vers se chantent, et sont accompagnés d’une grande symphonie, de danses, de ballets, avec des habits, et des décorations superbes, et de machines surprenantes.”

⁴Sima Godfrey (ed.), *The Anxiety of Anticipation* (New Haven: Yale University Press, 1984), p. 66.

These crises were frequently driven by debates over the moral and social implications of the theatrical productions, especially those featuring comic elements. When discussing the “tragic” or “comic” quality of the plots and characters, early modern French intellectuals generally borrowed from Aristotle’s *Poetics* (1449a), which clearly distinguishes both types and puts the accent on the inferior quality of comic characters.⁶ More specifically, Aristotle likens the lower quality of comedy with physical distortion, focusing on the notion of “mask”, potentially starring smirking mouths and funny-looking eyes. One straightforward conclusion that early modern commentators drew from the *Poetics* was the association of grotesque or vulgar acting with moral norms (*aïschron*, *αἰσχρον*, opposed to *kalos*, *καλός*).⁷ In the late sixteenth century, doctor Laurent Joubert argued that the desecration intrinsic to comedy made laughter “suggestively sexual”, and that women in particular were generally laughed *at* and not *with*.⁸ In this context, and especially following the fiery debate surrounding the tragicomedy *Le Cid* (premiered in 1636), many playwrights were incentivised to align with the moral and aesthetic standards of the time, often leading to the exclusion of comic elements to maintain the “purity” of serious dramatic works.

Many scholars have applied this reasoning, originally formulated for the historical study of spoken theatre, to the examination of seventeenth-century French opera after the creation of the ARM, arbitrarily setting aside the *comédie-ballet* genre marked by the famous artistic collaboration between Molière and Lully. The predominant scholarly focus on “serious” opera has been partly guided by the scarcity of sources related to comic genres, associated performers and performance practices.⁹ This focus has also been driven by influential publications that placed performers and the material conditions of opera business in the background and, instead, favoured the study of aesthetic quarrels. As a result, this scholarship has systematically amplified the dominance of the “tragic” over the “comic”, and has, at times, fostered the impression that *tragédies* would be devoid—if not constitutionally allergic—to comedy. As Lully’s contemporary Louis de Cahusac argued, Philippe Quinault had courted trouble by calling his operas *tragédies*, a designation that made comparison with spoken tragedy inevitable.¹⁰

Yet the overemphasis on literary theory as the primary lens for understanding early modern opera introduces significant biases, often based on anachronistic concepts that are discon-

⁶ Aristotle, *Aristotle in 23 Volumes*, vol. 23, trans. W.H. Fyfe (Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press; London: William Heinemann, 1932): “Comedy is a representation of inferior people, not indeed in the full sense of the word bad, but the laughable is a species of the base or ugly. It consists in some blunder or ugliness that does not cause pain or disaster, an obvious example being the comic mask which is ugly and distorted but not painful.”

⁷ In *Dans l’œil du miroir* (Paris: Odile Jacob, 1997, p. 131), Jean-Pierre Vernant writes that, in Ancient Greece, a person who would “put on airs” or “smirk”, in other words who would use social tactics of dissimulation, shared something with the feminine essence. The verb *akkizein* (to feign indifference or stupidity, to be coy) derives from *akko* (dissimulated) and relates to *akkizsthai* (a woman flirting with herself in front of the mirror). Proverbially, *Akkô* (associated with Lamnê or Lamia) designates a stupid woman.

⁸ Laurent Joubert, *Traité du ris contenant son essence, ses causes, et merveilbeus effais, curieusemant recerchés, raisonnés & observés* (Paris: Nicolas Chesneau, 1579).

⁹ François Moureau, for example, highlights in *De Gherardi à Watteau. Présence d’Arlequin sous Louis XIV* (Paris: Presses de l’Université Paris-Sorbonne, 1992, pp. 17–18) that when the troupe of the Comédie-Italienne was chased by the king on 14 May 1697, all of the administrative documents that were kept disappeared at the same time.

¹⁰ *La Danse*, vol. 3, pp. 94–6; trans. Caroline Wood and Graham Sadler, *French Baroque Opera: A Reader* (Aldershot: Ashgate, 2000), p. 46.

nected from the material reality of the performances.¹¹ Catherine Kintzler, a famous reference for the study of *tragédies en musique*'s poetics, affirms that the text is "sufficient" for "determining the concept of [operatic] genre" regardless of any other material condition or element.¹² She concedes that the *tragédie en musique* could be "ludic" at times, with "allusions, winks, and reminiscences" of comic traditions that created a "grimace" with the serious substance of the plot.¹³ And when dealing with explicit comic scenes, as in Lully's first operas, Kintzler dismisses them by stating that they were merely a hiccup from the Italian practices that would eventually quickly disappear without providing more specific details.¹⁴

Thus the dominant belief established by literary theorists is that the mix of comedy and tragedy in seventeenth-century operatic repertoire, regardless of proportion, should be regarded as "a generic blend that is undignified from the perspective of the [French] classical poetic system".¹⁵ This assumption is simply untrue. Not only did the Académie Royale de Musique have space for lighter, more comic-oriented plots, but also "serious" operatic works could clearly include comic elements. Lully frequently mixed comic characters with pathetic heroes on stage until relatively late in his career.¹⁶ And although the genre of the *tragédie en musique* became progressively more "tidy" and streamlined, the practice of integrating comic elements on the ARM stage never fully disappeared.

Recent scholarship on seventeenth-century theatrical practices has also revisited the role of parody and popular comedy in shaping operatic reception. Judith Le Blanc has argued that parody, in both occasional and full-scale dramatic forms, was not a marginal or derisive activity but a central part of the operatic ecosystem. Comic recycling—such as transforming operatic arias into *vaudevilles*—functioned as both tribute and critique, circulating widely across elite and popular venues. In this light, comic interventions should be read not as lapses in style but as intentional openings within a flexible cultural economy of musical reuse, where the same melodic material could migrate from the Opéra to the Pont-Neuf and back again.¹⁷

The issue of "comic" in operas is tightly tied to the cultural cross-dissemination between regions and professional troupes, particularly around the circulation of singing and acting

¹¹ Extreme examples of this can be found in psychoanalytical methods of enquiry, modelled after Catherine Clément's *L'Opéra ou la défaite des femmes* (Paris: Grasset, 1979), which nurture motivated reasoning, and therefore false narratives, about the operatic repertoire.

¹² Catherine Kintzler, "De La Pastorale à La Tragédie Lyrique: Quelques Éléments d'un Système Poétique", *Revue de Musicologie* 72, no. 1 (1986), p. 67. See also *Théâtre et opéra à l'âge classique, une famille étrangère* (Paris: Fayard, 2004); and *Poétique de l'opéra français de Corneille à Rousseau*, 2nd ed. Paris, Minerve, 2006.

¹³ Kintzler, *Théâtre et opéra à l'âge classique*, pp. 276–7: "[L]a tragédie lyrique se présentait, du fait de sa nature poétique, comme une sorte d'objet technique décalqué sur la tragédie dramatique: elle pouvait apparaître comme ludique. De ce fait, un certain effet comique en forme d'allusions, de clins d'œil, de reminiscences, n'en était pas exclu [...] [le ludique provient de ce] rapport grimaçant."

¹⁴ Kintzler, *Théâtre et opéra à l'âge classique*, p. 276, footnote 55: "[d]e telles scènes [comiques] disparaissent rapidement (c'est un mélange générique indigne du système poétique classique)".

¹⁵ *Ibid.*

¹⁶ In *Touched by the Graces. The Libretti of Philippe Quinault in the Context of French Classicism* (Birmingham, AL: Summa, 2001), Buford Norman, agrees with Kintzler that full-scale comic genre only got a foot in the Académie's door with *Platée* by Rameau (premiered at the French court in 1745 and performed again at the Académie in 1749), but also recognises that fragments of "pleasant" comedy were present in Quinault's early *tragédies en musique*.

¹⁷ Judith Le Blanc, "'Je sommes tous des Lully': Parodies d'opéras et circulation des airs chantés (XVIIe–XVIIIe siècles)", *Musicologies nouvelles*, 2019, pp. 58–66.

practices across Europe. This fact necessitates studying the presence of comedy in operatic work outside the sole scope of the written text. This methodological approach has been increasingly adopted in twenty-first century scholarship. Researchers with a strong interest in the influence of Italian practices over seventeenth-century French repertoire have followed that method when exploring French *tragédies en musique*, *pastorales*, and *ballets*.¹⁸ In parallel, other scholars have investigated the importance of French comic genres in the repertoire (e.g. operatic parodies, puppet shows) performed outside the Académie Royale de Musique, generally at the fairs, and the interrelations they entertained with serious operatic works.¹⁹

This article aims to dive further into the study of comedy in the repertoire and performance practices at the ARM during the reign of Louis XIV. The multiplicity of comic elements at different “levels” of the artwork, sometimes overlapping, is not easy to summarise neatly. These elements may appear in different characters, situations, single gestures or words, music, dance, and overall tone. Mythological characters could share the stage with non-aristocratic roles, such as servants, nurses, and other characters of low social origins who could provide comic relief to the main plot. Unsurprisingly, the sheer variety of “comical” expressions often proves disorienting, perhaps encouraging their omission from critical engagement with early modern opera.

To better grasp how the practice appeared in operas performed at the ARM, I will focus here on individual performers and the level of interpersonal relationships (including artists, administrators, and members of the audience) that structured the creative process underpinning opera production at the ARM. While not a sociological study of laughter at the Opéra, this article will occasionally examine the ambiguous effects of comedy and will therefore integrate, when available, the reaction and commentary of contemporaries.

The transversal approach used here, which brings together repertoire, cast, and performance practice from 1669 until 1715, contributes to a broader discussion on the notion of typecasting (or *emploi*, in French), which has recently come under greater scrutiny.²⁰ Against ready-made schematic categories that assume an artificially air-tight principle of role categorisation throughout the early modern period, a close analysis of the Académie’s troupe at its beginnings demonstrates the paramount importance of the performer as a regulative force in delineating roles’ consistency and typecasting. Thus, it also raises important issues related to the structure and functioning of the Académie Royale de Musique and its relationship with the market of French singers during the long seventeenth century.

¹⁸For a comprehensive overview of Barbara Nestola, *L’air italien sur la scène des théâtres parisiens (1687–1715)* (Turnhout: Brepols, 2020). See also Jérôme de La Gorce, “L’académie royale de musique et la Comédie-Italienne sous le règne de Louis XIV deux entreprises de spectacle en rivalité?”, in *L’Opéra de Paris, la Comédie-Française et l’Opéra-Comique: Approches comparées (1669–2010)* (Paris: Publications de l’École nationale des Chartes, 2012), pp. 17–24; Emanuele De Luca, “La circulation des acteurs italiens et des genres dramatiques dans la première moitié du XVIIIe siècle”, in *L’Opéra de Paris* (op. cit.), pp. 241–54.

¹⁹See, for example, Françoise Rubellin seminal publication’s *Théâtre de La Foire. Anthologie de Pièces Inédites 1712–1736* (Éditions Espaces 34, 2005); and Pauline Beaucé, *Parodies d’opéra au siècle des Lumières: évolution d’un genre comique* (Presses Universitaires de Rennes, 2013).

²⁰See Céline Candiard, “Emplois Comiques et Répertoire Moliéresque: Enjeux Dramaturgiques d’un Principe de Distribution”, *Agon* 7 (2015) [online]; Lola Salem, “Emplois and casting at the Académie Royale de Musique: Female Opera Singers and their Roles from 1669 to 1715”, Ph.D. dissertation, University of Oxford, 2022.

I. A Comic Courtier? Jean-Baptiste Lully's Early Career and the Politics of Performance

During the seventeenth century, comic and tragic elements in operatic plots were not quite like water and oil. This was largely because opera, from its inception, lacked the same degree of verisimilitude that French spoken theatre, grounded on Aristotelian rules, sought to uphold. Opera's hybrid nature, combining music, singing, written poetic text, dance, gestures and decors, led some contemporaries to criticise it as "monstrous"—that is as a genre born deformed and contrary to the natural order. Yet it was precisely this hybridity that allows opera to accommodate a broad variety of effects on stage.²¹

The blending of comic and serious elements in French operas represented a natural prolongation of the *ballets de cour* and Italian operatic works. The former relied on a principle of variety, with a succession of brief sequences that lent themselves to light-hearted and even comic expressions. The latter, which evolved alongside the flourishing of commercial arts across Northern Italy, integrated comic passages and specialised characters dealing with comedy. This blend grew in importance during the seventeenth century, despite some criticism.²² Comic roles added spice to the main plotlines. They were embodied by singers and dancers alike to symbolise on stage a variety of people and creatures from fantasised foreign lands (e.g. Turkey, Spain, Maghreb) and fictional landscapes. For instance, in *Le nozze di Teti e di Peleo* (1639) by Francesco Cavalli (on a libretto by Orazio Persiani, and in collaboration with the choreographer Giovan Battista Balbi), the large number of dances (some using voices, others just instruments) offered fertile ground for developing comic features. One scene featured Bacco and Sileno who "praise[d] the virtues of wine", as well as fauns and Bacchantes in the choruses, which were deliberately designed to provoke smiles.

This Italian tradition was also palatable in the repertoire of spoken theatre. Céline Candiard has shown in her meticulous inquiry about the comic roles of slaves and valets in the Roman theatrical repertoire that, prior to the restructurings of the Théâtre-Italien in Paris (in 1680 and 1716), these two *emplois* (stocks of roles) were merged with the physical and spectacular characteristics of its performers.²³ As "playmakers", Candiard argues that "the strong

²¹ For the definition of "monstrous", see Pierre Richelet's *Dictionnaire français* (Geneva, Jean Herman Widerhold, 1685, 2:39), the 1694 *Dictionnaire de l'Académie française* (Paris, Jean-Baptiste Coignard, 1694, 2:83), and the *Encyclopédie* (10:671). Charles Dill in *Monstrous Opera Rameau and the Tragic Tradition* (Princeton University Press, 1998), gives a compelling account of the ways in which the term was used in the context of seventeenth century opera criticism.

²² For example, Giovanni Mario Crescimbeni spoke about *Giasone* by Cavalli and Giacinto Andrea Cicognini (premiered in 1649 in Venice) in very harsh terms: "[...] with it he brought the end of acting, and consequently, of true and good comedy as well as tragedy. Since to stimulate to a greater degree with novelty the jaded taste of the spectators, equally nauseated by the vileness of comic things and the seriousness of tragic ones ... [he] united them, mixing kings and heroes and other illustrious personages with buffoons and servants and the lowest men with unheard of monstrosity. This concoction of characters was the reason for the complete ruin of the rules of poetry, which went so far into disuse that not even locution was considered, which, forced to serve music, lost its purity, and became filled with idiocies." (Trans. Ellen Rosand, *Opera in Seventeenth-Century Venice*, [Berkeley: University of California Press, 1991], p. 434.) Note that the first operatic Italian poets working in Florence tried to exclude comic elements from their plots, which material derived from classical myths, ancient history, and the pastoral universe, with some rare exceptions. For example, elements of comedy can be found in Guidiccioni and Cavalieri's *La disperazione di Fileno* (1590), in the satyrs of Salvadori and Gagliano's *Flora* (1628), and in Titon's lament appearing in Chiabrera and Caccini's *Il rapimento di Cefalo* (1600).

²³ Céline Candiard, *Esclaves et valets vedettes dans les comédies de la Rome antique et de la France d'Ancien Régime*

spectacular identity of these performers” blurred the lines between the actors and their roles’ characteristics.²⁴

Seventeenth-century French contemporaries tended to associate the integration of comic performance and practice in operatic music with Italian culture, whether they operated within or alongside serious plots. Its transfer into the French repertoire is the proof of a fruitful and long-lasting influence of Italian practices. This phenomenon has been explored by several scholars, notably Michel Gilot, Jean Serroy, and Barbara Nestola.²⁵ And while Italian authors working in Paris may have been encouraged to reduce the comic dimension from the plots they used (as part of a broader strategy to make their work more appropriate for their new audience), the adaptation process rarely erased it completely.²⁶

This interplay between composition and casting had a notable impact on the way singers refined their skills, which could facilitate the development and sustainability of their careers. Indeed some Italian singers (generally tenors, basses, or *castrati*) chose to specialise in comic roles, developing recognisable performance “types” that were readily identifiable for the audience. The castrato Tomaso Bovi, for example, who lived at the Venetian Grimani palace, performed comic roles in the Grimani theaters, generally under the traits of a servant.²⁷ He frequently took on the part of the old nurse (*vecchia*), which was typically performed by men and usually supplanted the need for a female confidant in the plot.

Humour, tightly tethered to the social context in which it arises, required additional care when translated across cultural borders. Performing comedy in opera also required a degree of specialisation; yet not all singers were inclined, or able, to undertake such comic roles. Correctly selecting (and occasionally training) singers was evidently key for the success of an operatic performance. This was particularly relevant when the repertoire would eventually be translated for a new audience with distinct cultural references and expectations, like Italian operas were for the French court in the 1630s and 1640s. Cardinal Jules Mazarin (1602–61), acutely aware of the challenges posed by the reception of Italian repertoire in France, took a personal interest in the recruitment of performers. He alluded to this in a letter to Abbot Buti, librettist for Cavalli’s *Ercole amante* (performed in 1662 in Paris):

You must examine the singers you choose as carefully as the instrumentalists as each must be skilled in his art in order to produce a performance in which there may be no cause for

(Paris: Honoré Champion, 2017), p. 357.

²⁴Idem.

²⁵Michel Gilot and Jean Serroy, *La comédie à l’âge classique*, Paris, Belin Sup, 1997, pp. 58–62, 173–81, 244–57; Barbara Nestola, *L’air italien sur la scène des théâtres parisiens (1687–1715)* (Turnhout: Brepols, 2020).

²⁶For example, after its premiere in March 1647, Luigi Rossi’s *Orfeo* (using a libretto from Francesco Buti) undergo this re-writing process. Nevertheless, even after the amendments made around April and May 1647, the opera retained some comic elements; cf. Barbara Nestola, “L’opéra italien à la cour de France : réception et adaptation d’un objet étranger (1645–1662)”, *Bulletin du Centre de recherche du château de Versailles* 11 (2016), §4 [online]. Even in spoken theatre, the persistence of comedy in Italian works is clear. Guy Boquet argues that the intensification of the competition, with French authors such as Corneille, Molière, and Racine, accentuated the use of *lazzi* with even more grotesque gestures and textual obscenities (“Les Comédiens Italiens à Paris au temps de Louis XIV”, *Revue d’Histoire Moderne & Contemporaine* 26, no. 3 [1979], p. 429).

²⁷ASV, AN, Testamenti, b. 1197, no. 291. For a list of Bovi’s roles at S. Giovanni Grisostomo between 1678 and 1700, see also Harris S. Saunders, “Repertoire of a Venetian Opera House”, Ph.D. dissertation, Harvard, 1987, pp. 448–59.

mockery. You know well that the French are prone to that.²⁸

These concerns highlight the importance of networking for artists during that time. Singers needed to market themselves strategically in order to be cast appropriately, while authors had to engage regularly with them regularly on a personal basis to identify their skills and potential.

Jean-Baptiste Lully understood these dynamics well. The Florentine-born composer, eager to see his opera business succeed under Louis XIV's patronage, learnt a great deal from his early experience at the French court prior to gaining control of the ARM in 1672. In fact, during this period of rich musical experimentation, humour served him as a ladder to success, combined with a sophisticated grasp of social networks and an astute eye for talent.

Lully, now traditionally remembered as the leading composer figure of the ARM, did not begin his career in France as one. His successive appointments, first to the household of the Grande Mademoiselle (Anne-Marie-Louise d'Orléans) between 1646 and 1652, then to the Chambre du Roi, reveal a man of versatile talents who initially navigated the court circles as a sort of "generalist" entertainer.²⁹ His strong musical skills first manifested through his status as a performer, which was not uncommon at the time. Indeed many musicians would make themselves known through performance first, which allowed them to contribute additional dance or music to the plot before being rewarded with the official title of composers for these.³⁰

Lully frequently deployed comic effects on stage in order to seduce the audience and make a name for himself at the court. It is also likely that his light-hearted, occasionally frivolous or irreverent personality helped him forge a closer bond with the sovereign himself. The character of the Grande Mademoiselle, inclined to humour and laughter, probably encouraged Lully's own mischievousness and occasional insolence.³¹ Despite the upheavals of the Fronde (1648–53), the music organised for the Grande Mademoiselle during that time remained very joyful.³² It echoed the repertoire of the Foire (fair) Saint-Germain where one could see "many different smirks", as the eminent author of *Le Roman comique*, Paul Scarron, described.³³ The Orléans family held this Foire in particular esteem, and the financial accounts of the Grande Mademoiselle confirm that she benefitted from allocated funds for her amusement there be-

²⁸Letter from August 1659, trans. Henry Prunières, *L'opéra italien en France avant Lully* (Paris: Champion, 1913), p. 231: "Je vous prie de vouloir bien examiner les personnes qu'on prendra tant pour chanter que pour jouer [...] car ils faut qu'ils soient chacun executant en son métier afin de former un corps de musique duquel il n'y ait pas lieu de se moquer, car vous savez bien que les François y sont assez disposés."

²⁹After meeting with the Chevalier de Guise (Gaston d'Orléans) in Tuscany in 1645, Lully was called to work as an Italian tutor in for his daughter, the Grande Mademoiselle (Anne-Marie-Louise d'Orléans). See Jérôme de La Gorce, *Jean-Baptiste Lully* (Paris: Fayard, 2002), pp. 25–7 and 31.

³⁰Note, for example, the case of Michel Mazuel who composed bits of music for different ballets before being made composer for the Twenty-Four Violins (Vingt-quatre violons) in May 1654 (F-Pan, O1* 17, f° 165 and 165v0). Likewise, the predecessor of the *brevet* received by Lully, Lazaro Lazzarini, had a similar career path (see La Gorce, *Lully*, p. 63).

³¹La Gorce, *Lully*, pp. 33–5. The laughter of the Grande Mademoiselle is noticed by some contemporaries. Loret mentioned it heard, for example, before the performance of the ballet *Les Fêtes de Bacchus* on 2 May 1651 at the Palais Royal (Jean Loret, *La Muze historique ou recueil des lettres en very continent les novellas du temps*, ed. J. Ravenel and Ed. V. de La Pelouze [Paris: P. Jannet, 1857], t. 1, p. 115, Letter of 7 May 1651).

³²La Gorce, *Lully*, p. 49. See testimony by Loret who mentioned several balls, particularly at the end of 1651 and at the start of 1652 (*La Muze historique*, t. 1, p. 186, Letter of 10 December 1651; and p. 202, Letter of 14 January 1652).

³³Paul Scarron, *La Foire Saint Germain, dédié à Monsieur* (Paris, 1643), pp. 6–7.

tween 1647 and 1650.³⁴

Exposed to these forms of entertainment, while surrounded by a diverse group of musicians and performers gravitating around the Grande Mademoiselle, Lully quickly understood the vital role of comic expression across opera's textual, musical, and choreographic dimensions—the latter being particularly enjoyed by the French audience. Moreover, Lully knew that this blend directly relied on the careful selection and training of performers. Between 1646 and 1652, he took advantage of the network around the Grande Mademoiselle to consolidate not only his own musical training, but also his professional network.

It is presumed that Nicolas Métru and his protégé Nicolas Gigault, both organists at the Jesuit church on Rue Saint-Antoine (now Saint-Paul Church, near the Guise's apartments), and François Roberday (whose more informal musical activity formed part of a broader set of artistic endeavours) acted, in one way or another, as mentors for Lully's musical development.³⁵ Lully could also have learnt from other artists who were also active at the same time. Jacques Cordier (1580–1653), known as Bocan, was praised as “the miracle of his century not only with regard to dance, but also for the violin and for composing perfectly-pitched, agreeable, and harmonious arias.”³⁶ Jean Regnault (1624–1701), also a dancer, probably played an important role for introducing Lully to the king's service after 1652 for *Le Ballet de la Nuit*. Michel Lambert (ca. 1610–1696), who would become Lully's father-in-law in 1662, had published a famous singing treatise *Remarques curieuses sur l'art de bien chanter* (1668) dedicated to the Grande Mademoiselle.

Soon after Lully started his employment at the Grande Mademoiselle's household, Lambert and other talented musicians, including the singer Hilaire Dupuis (1625–1709) who would later feature in Lully's ballets, performed several times in Fontainebleau.³⁷ It is impossible to prove if Lully attended these concerts or not.³⁸ Likewise, nothing can confirm his presence during the performance of *Orfeo* by Luigi Rossi in 1647 at the Palais Royal. Nevertheless, the frequent presence of the Grande Mademoiselle at these events eventually brought Lully closer with the musical scene that regularly entertained the court.

The *Mascarade de la Foire Saint-Germain* (7, 8 and 11 March 1652) was Lully's first official work. It is the only score that explicitly showcases his artistic output during his time as employee of the Grande Mademoiselle. It was preceded on 8 February by a “beautiful ballet, which was found charming and a bit mad [...] because there was comedy and farce” during which the violinists working for the Grande Mademoiselle played.³⁹ It attests to the ethos of the band, including Lully's, who likely performed the role of a “crieur de rats” (cheese tarts seller) in the fifth *entrée*. This comic character would have suited the expressiveness of his traits, gestures and attitudes.

³⁴F-Pa ms. 4211, f^o 293v^o, 299, 303, and 306.

³⁵La Gorce, *Lully*, pp. 39–41; *Raisons qui prouvent manifestement que les compositeurs de musique ou les musiciens qui se servent des clavecins, luths et autres instruments d'harmonie, pour l'exprimer, n'ont jamais été et ne peuvent pas être de la communauté des anciens jongleurs et ménestrels de Paris* (Paris, 1695), p. 33.

³⁶Henri Sauval, *Histoire et recherches des Antiquités de la Ville de Paris* (Paris, 1724), t. 1, p. 329, my translation.

³⁷See Henry Prunières, “Les singulières aventures de M. Dassoucy, musicien et poète burlesque”, *La Revue Musicale* 180, January 1938, p. 23.

³⁸La Gorce, *Lully*, p. 45.

³⁹Loret, *La Muze historique*, t. 1, p. 211.

After entering the Chambre du Roi in 1652 as a twenty-years-old violinist, Lully continued to build his reputation as a performer who frequently used the mask of comic roles. In the highly successful *Ballet de la Nuit* (March 1653), Lully played five different characters across the first two sections of the play.⁴⁰ After appearing first under the traits of a shepherd (*berger*), then as a soldier with a moustache and a large feathery hat, Lully came back on stage as a poor person—emblematic of the Court of Miracles—in the company of his colleagues Lambert, du Moustier, and de Lorge, all portraying crippled characters. The “grotesque” nature of the scene and the “burlesque” quality of the music and dance were the “cause of an entertainment that provoked incessant laughter”.⁴¹ Later, Lully took on the part of a transvestite, acting as one of the three Graces in the pantomime “Noces de Thétis”. Finally, partnered again with du Moustier (likely as Sosie) during the “silent comedy of Amphion”, styled in the manner of the *commedia dell’arte*. Both characters disguised themselves in order to play tricks to others. Additionally, Lully likely had a hand in modelling the variety of ballets, which mixed several types of regional dances, notably Spanish ones.⁴² The Florentine was well rewarded for that performance: on 16 March 1653, Lully received a *brevet* appointing him official composer of instrumental music for the king.⁴³

Following the successful *Ballet de la Nuit*, Lully continued to advance his musical career thanks to the performance of comic and comic-adjacent characters, using humour as a means of ingratiating himself with Louis XIV. In April 1654, Lully appeared as a Fury (*furie*) and later as a follower of Chiron clothed as a Native American in *Les Noces de Pélée et de Thétis*. That same year, he performed in *Le Ballet des Proverbes* and *Le Ballet du Temps*. On 4 February 1655, *Le Ballet des Plaisirs* aimed to provide entertainment during the Carnival period. For this production, Lully featured in four of its twenty-four *entrées*, two of them shared with the king. Alongside Louis XIV, Lully first appeared as an Egyptian tasked to dance “a great buffoonery with basque percussions and castanets”, then as a debauched person returning from a cabaret. In the rest of the plot, Lully continued to perform typified comic roles, such as a ridicule old man and a satyr in an *entrée* particularly admired by the audience, also starring the famous singer Claude Munier Saint-Helme. On 16 January 1656, *Le Ballet de Psyché ou de la Puissance de l’Amour* gave Lully yet another occasion to shine before the king. This ballet made a lasting impression with the bold staging of “Miss Mancini” (probably Olympe) as a denuded nymph beside the monarch.

This period coincided with the end of the Fronde and Louis XIV’s return to Paris. Many nobles who revolted against him, including the Orléans family, went into exile. Away from his former patrons and their musical networks, Lully realigned himself with the king’s circle. Louis XIV had at his disposal a diverse pool of talents, including Italian performers whose knowledge, skills, and inventiveness matched well the practice of blending comic passages with more serious plots. Crucially, Lully did not only request the services of Italians. He collab-

⁴⁰They are described by Loret’s *Muze historique* and some drawings of costumes that are conserved by the Bibliothèque de l’Institut (Ms. 1004).

⁴¹Loret, *La Muze historique*, t. 1, p. 348, Letter from 8 March 1653.

⁴²That variety of dances is described in a letter from 28 February 1653 written by the Pope’s nuncio (Rome, Secrete Archives of the Vatican, Nunziatura di Francia, 107). La Gorce (*Lully*, p. 61) suggests this by reminding the reader that the Medici in Florence, where Lully came from, welcomed many Spanish performers.

⁴³F-Pan, O1* 17, f° 165.

orated with French singers as well, intentionally mixing performers of diverse training in his productions in order to showcase his versatility in both French and Italian styles, with the continued intention to feature here and there carefully chosen comic elements.

This strategy is already evident in *Le Ballet de Psyché, ou de la puissance de l'amour* (1656). In the twelfth *entrée* of the second part, Lully created a polyphonic effect by writing for a diverse vocal ensemble. The effect relied on four allegories (Fear, Suspicion, Despair, Jealousy) respectively performed by Anna Bergerotti, Gian Francesco Tagliavacca, Claude Munier Saint-Helme, and a "Signora Tondi", in alternance with a chorus.⁴⁴ The same principle of style and vocal variety is visible in following productions.

For instance, in the fourth *entrée* of *Le Ballet de l'Amour Malade* (1657), with a libretto by Francesco Buti, Lully juxtaposed a French and an Italian aria, both with a *ritournelle* of their own. The "Chanson contre les jaloux" ("Song against the jealous ones"), sung by Hilaire Dupuy, follows the formal plan of contemporary French air, with a binary structure, a dynamic median caesura accompanied by a change of meter, and varied repetition of the last line of the verse. The French-styled aria is directly followed by "E che sarebbe amor senza coquette" ("What would love be without *coquettes*?"), a tripartite structure (with the suggestion of a *dal-segno* repeat of the opening section) and alternates a slow refrain with fast passages in a style reminiscent of Cavalli's work. The humour here is subtle but far from absent. In the French passage, the harmonic colouring—blurring A minor with its relative major—reinforces the ambiguity of its stance on jealousy in romantic relationships. It leaves the spectator wondering: is this a sincere lament, or merely a wry complaint about lovers who take offence at libertinage? Likewise, in the Italian passage, the rapid shifts in harmony (oscillating between A and D mainly) and metre imply a coded joke between the artist and the audience. The lighter undertone of the message is further highlighted in the orchestral passages and the dance that immediately precede and follow the segment, a (potentially ironic) celebration of the dancing "brave jealous ones" ("les braves jaloux") who dispute the attention of the two singing *coquettes*, the French and the Italian ones.

Bergerotti's and Munier Saint-Helme's individual fames served Lully's career well. Bergerotti's past successes in Italy and triumph in France (where she stayed between 1655 and 1669) catalysed Lully's own reputation among the court. Already in 1655, following a concert during which both singers and Lully participated, Jean Loret testified the mutual service they provided to one another in terms of social aura.⁴⁵ Loret highlighted further the specific bond between Bergerotti and Lully by outlining the efforts that the composer made for magnifying the actress in the *Le Ballet de Psyché* and *La Galanterie du temps* (where she performed the allegorical character of La Mode).⁴⁶ She was also instrumental for some key humorous scenes

⁴⁴Benserade, *Ballets pour Louis XIV*, I, 321. See La Gorce, *Lully*, pp. 87–8.

⁴⁵Loret, *La Muse historique*, II, p. 47: 'Une musique sans égale/Par ses accents doux et vainqueurs/Avait charmé plus de cent cœurs/Dans la chambre de notre Reine,/Qui de gens choisis était pleine./Saint-Helme, qui dans les concerts/Passe pour un des plus experts,/Et certaine Anne d'Italie,/Dont la voix est plus que jolie,/Eux seuls mêlèrent leurs accords,(Digne d'avoir bien de la vogue)./C'était un charmant dialogue/De la guerre avec la paix,/Un des beaux qu'on chanta jamais,/Et dont l'air, presque à l'improviste,/Fut noté par le sieur Baptiste.'

⁴⁶Regarding *Psyché*: 'Et l'aimable Bergeroti [sic]/Faisait entre dans son parti/Mainte âme excellente et choisie/Quoiqu'elle fût la Jalousie.' (Loret, *La Muse historique*, 154 [Letter of 29 January 1656].) Regarding the *Galanterie*: 'Et cette autre agréable Brune,/Dont l'excellence est peu commune./La Signora Bergerota,/Vers la fin, les cœurs enchantés,/Ayant dans la douce harmonie,/Un rare et ravissant génie.' (Idem [Letter of 5 February 1656].)

in *Le Ballet de la raillerie* (1659), as will be discussed below.

The performance of Cavalli's *Xerse* on 22 November 1660 at the French court called for the integration of dance, notably because of the contemporary taste but also because many did not understand most of the Italian lyrics. Six scenes were therefore added, representing a perfect opportunity for Lully to shine. He appeared on stage under different traits, as a "transvestite" Scaramouche acting "in-between two disguised doctors", and as a "boat leader" with, under his orders, slaves wearing monkeys ridiculously dressed ("fagotins") and sailors playing the *trompette marine* (tromba marina).⁴⁷ The libretto also indicates that one of the *matassins* (a mad fool of buffoon performing comic dances in pantomime) was performed by "Baptiste".⁴⁸ The addition may well have been lifted from *Le Ballet de l'Amour Malade*, itself inspired by the fashionable trend of comic doctor roles in spoken theatre at the time. In the fifth *entrée* of the ballet, a group of eleven doctors including one holding a "doctorate in stupidities" ("thèse d'âne") gather around Scaramouche. The motif resurfaces in the sixth *entrée* of *Le Ballet des Arts* (1663) in which Lully arranged several dances for surgeons, doctors, and crippled—a few years ahead of Molière's *Le Médecin malgré lui* (1666), which would immortalise the trope.

Through the 1660s, Lully's fast-growing fame coincided with Louis XIV's adoption of the sun as royal symbol.⁴⁹ Aware of the criticism directed at his frivolous character, which included mockeries of his sexual conduct, Lully sought to counterbalance his reputation for comic entertainment with the fashioning of a more dignified persona.⁵⁰ Under the guise of a "florentine gentleman", Lully received increasing largesses from Louis XIV.⁵¹ In December 1661, his gifts were legitimised by the fact that Lully was considered as "[capable to compose] music of all sorts, including several beautiful pieces of dance and singing that were composed in different languages."⁵² Lully further honed his serious style by experimenting with sacred music. His first *Jubilate Dei* (1660), in particular, enjoyed a great success.

Yet more than ever, Lully remained committed to appear on stage as much as possible for the entertainment of the king, which included, as always, significant comic elements.⁵³ Although Italian musicians were progressively leaving the court in the 1660s, Italian comedy

Additionally, the newspaper *La Muse royale* also commented in 22 February 1656: 'La Signora Bergerotti,/Objet de grâces assorti/Pour l'amant y fit des merveilles/À charmer toutes les oreilles.'

⁴⁷*Xerxes, Comédie en musique del Signor Francesco Cavalli. Avec six Entrées de Ballet qui servent d'Intermèdes à la Comédie*, Paris, Robert Ballard, 1660, pp. 18 and 21. Note that the *trompette marine* is also quoted by Monsieur Jourdain in the comic *Bourgeois Gentilhomme* (1670) as an "instrument that [he likes] and would enjoy playing" (act II, scene 1).

⁴⁸F-Pn, dept. Littérature et art, YD-1212. V: Pier Francesco Cavalli, *Xerxes: comédie en musique, avec six entrées de ballet* (Paris, 1660), Entrée Les Matassins, p. 36 (also numbered LWV 12/11 in the modern edition by Henry Prunières, 1933).

⁴⁹Henry Prunières went as far as suggesting that Lully himself might have encouraged that departure. In "Lully and the *Académie de Musique et de Danse*", *The Musical Quarterly* 11, no. 4 (1925), p. 530, he argued (my translation): "Colbert, who had just succeeded Fouquet, had no love for [Italian artists], and upheld the principle of protection in matters of art as well as in industry and commerce. Lully therefore shifted his ground and became the champion of French musicians. He had the Italian singers dismissed from court one by one, after so arranging matters that they were never heard."

⁵⁰F-Pn Musique, Rés. 1593 (5), p. 342, quoted by La Gorce in *Lully*, p. 795, footnote no. 39.

⁵¹See, for example, a poem on Lully's sexual tendencies in Paris, Archives des Affaires étrangères, France 911, f° 242vo.

⁵²Lettres de naturalisé, déposées chez Charles, notaire, le 23 juillet 1662, F-Pan, Minutier central, XLVI-85.

⁵³La Gorce, *Lully*, pp. 134–5.

would only disappear from Paris, for a little while, on 4 May 1697, with the closure of the Comédie-Italienne; thus it remained a strong benchmark for theatrical expression and success.⁵⁴ As before, the choice to integrate comedy in his work was part of Lully's broader strategy of strengthening relationships between himself and other musicians.⁵⁵

Following the success of *Le Ballet de l'Amour Malade*, the dialectic between French and Italian styles and performers was regularly staged in Lully's works. This competition was explored, for instance, in *Le Ballet de la raillerie* (1659) and *Le Ballet royal de l'Impatience* (1661), through operatic dialogues and French *récits*. The former was based on a libretto by Isaac de Benserade (1613–91), renowned who for his ability to write both serious and comic works.⁵⁶ It featured several ensembles built around key singers, including the famous Bergerotti, whose "voice [was] so precious to the Louvre".⁵⁷ She first appeared in the Prologue as part of a trio, performing Folly (La Folie, La Piazza), alongside Hilaire Dupuis as Wisdom (La Sagesse, La Saviezza), and Anne Chabanceau de La Barre (1628–88) under the traits of the role-title Mockery (La Raillerie, La Beffa). La Barre, employed at the Chambre du Roi, was herself recognised for her manifold vocal talents.⁵⁸ Hilaire Dupuis (1625–1709), a student of Pierre de Nyert and Michel de Lambert, whose "delicious voice delighted princes and kings and can even please the angels [...] presented her unique gentleness in [the delightful *Ballet de la raillerie*]", also displayed a great range of skills, impersonating French cultural allegories as well as several Italian and comic roles recorded in opera casts after 1659.⁵⁹

Then in the intermezzo, Bergerotti would confront La Barre in an aesthetic battle opposing Italian Music to French Music, which they respectively personified. Finally, in the Epilogue, a new series of allegories gathered once more the Bergerotti (Fashion, La Mode) with Dupuis (Contrariety, La Contrariété), La Barre (Criticism, La Critique), and their male colleagues Claude Le Gros (Ballet) and Meunier Saint-Elme (Disgusted, Le Dégouté), ranked by Loret as "above the most excellent" singers.⁶⁰ Le Gros, a singer at the Chambre du Roi and Chapelle royale, like his colleague Laurent Hébert, could sing extremely high; his falsetto (*contrefaiseur*) allowed him to perform as a *dessus or bas-dessus* in the 8th *entrée* of the same ballet.

Lully also frequently integrated "grotesque" scenes in Italian—a term defined in Richelet's *Dictionnaire françois*, 1680, as "humorously ridiculous". These appear in *Le Ballet des bien-venus* (1655) and *Le Ballet royal de l'impatience* (1661), and later works *Monsieur de Pourceaugnac* (1669) and *Le Bourgeois gentilhomme* (1670). For example, Lully places at the

⁵⁴Cf. Guy Boquet, "Les Comédiens Italiens", pp. 434–8.

⁵⁵La Gorce, *Lully*, p. 135: "Les différents rôles qu'il s'appliquait à remplir avec tant de zèle dans les spectacles contribuaient à le rapprocher des interprètes qu'il dirigeait tout en les côtoyant de plus en plus."

⁵⁶Benserade first comedy, *Iphis and Lante* (1634), addresses the topic of female homosexuality in the form of cross-dressing. Many of his poems were entertaining, gallant, and amusing. In particular, his adaptation of Ovid's *Metamorphoses* for Louis XIV's 12-year-old son (commissioned in 1674) demonstrates his inventiveness with regards to traditional, mythical material, which is not afraid to blend comedy and seriousness.

⁵⁷Loret, *Lettre Huitième*, t. 3, p. 25, vv. 223–4.

⁵⁸Lisandro Abadie, "Anne de La Barre (1628–1688): biographie d'une chanteuse de cour", *Revue de Musicologie*, 94/1 (2008), pp. 5–44; Marcelle Benoît, *Musiques de Cour 1661–1733, Chapelle, Chambre, Écurie* (Paris, Picard, 1971), p. 3.

⁵⁹Loret, *Lettre Huitième*, t. 3, p. 25, vv. 213–18. See complete list of Dupuis' roles in French and Italian in Catherine Massip, *L'art de bien chanter: Michel Lambert (1610–1696)* (Société française de musicologie, 1999), p. 73–4.

⁶⁰Loret, *Lettre Huitième*, t. 3, p. 25, vv. 223–4.

beginning of the second part of the *Ballet des bienvenus* a “Récit crotisque [sic] Italian”, with vocal and instrumental parts including “queerly dressed characters, with many postures and pleasant actions of the body”.⁶¹ Another “Récit crotisque” [sic] in *Le Ballet royal de l’impatience* represents a comic conversation between a music teacher and a homophonic chorus of his disciples, all sung in Italian.⁶² In *Le Bourgeois gentilhomme*, Lully famously sang the character of the Mufti during the Act IV, whose melodies and lyrics are intended to trigger laughter, and around whom many comic dances representing a “Turkish ceremony” are performed. The first *récit*, “Se ti sabir...”, uses *Lingua franca* (also known as Sabir), a pidgin language developed by sailors in the Mediterranean Sea since the Middle Ages for facilitating communication, conduct trade and diplomacy.

The amalgamation of comic, music, and dance in the *comédies-ballets* produced by Lully and Molière have been thoroughly investigated by a series of literary and musicological studies, in particular that of Claude Abraham, Louis Auld, Nicholas Cronk, Gérard Defaux, Stephen Fleck, Charles Mazouer, Robert McBride, Buford Norman, and John Powell.⁶³ The inclusion of buffoonish characters such as *matassins*—carnival fools borrowed from *commedia dell’arte*—punctuated many of Lully’s operas and ballets with stylised absurdity. As Kenley McDowell has shown, these figures brought in choreographic grotesquerie via exaggerated Pyrrhic or gigue rhythms, often appearing in final entrées or festive interludes. Lully featured them in *Psyché* (1671), *Monsieur de Pourceaugnac* (1669), and other ballets as agents of comic relief, medical satire, or burlesque closure—in one instance, with apothecaries wielding syringes instead of swords.⁶⁴

Around the mid-1660s, many of Lully’s airs and dance music compositions began gaining fame even outside of France. Among this repertoire, a light and entertaining bourrée, identified as the “Bore de Baptist” in an English source, contributed to bringing him significant recognition abroad. This humorous piece, reportedly favoured by jovial priests, underscores once more the important role that comedy played in the development of Lully’s career and persona.⁶⁵

As Italian artists departed from the French court, Lully reconfigured his professional network. His inner circle of singers focused on people like Anne Chabanceau de La Barre, Hilaire Dupuis, Mlle Saint-Christophe, and Anne Fonteaux de Cercamanan, with whom Lully had

⁶² Although the lyrics do not appear in the printed libretto of the ballet, the music is preserved in a manuscript copied by the librarian of the Musique du Roi (André Danican Philidor *l’ainé*).

⁶³ See, for example, Louis Auld, “Lully’s Comic Art”, in *Jean-Baptiste Lully: Actes du colloque / Kongressbericht Saint-Germain-en-Laye-Heidelberg 1987*, ed. Jérôme de La Gorce and Herbert Schneider (Laaber: Laaber-Verlag, 1990), pp. 17–30; Stephen Fleck, “Enjoyment and Subversion in the Comedy-Ballets”, *Cahiers Du Dix-septième* 7, no. 1 (1997), pp. 1–9.

⁶⁴ McDowell Kenley, “Mad Fools and the Praise of Folly: matassins and the ballets of Lully, Destouches and Campra”, *Early Music History* 45, no. 3 (2017), pp. 445–57.

⁶⁵ Bolognese priest, Sebastian Locatelli, describes it in reference to another priest described as “very pleasant” and “extremely gay” (“fort amiable” and of an “extrême gaité”) who sang Lully’s *bourrée* in a hotel. See Sebastiano Locatelli (Eurillo Battisodo), *Voyage en France, mœurs et costumes françaises (1664–1665)*, ed. A. Vautier (Paris, Alphonse Picard et fils, 1905), p. 78 and 79; *The Dancing Master: Plain and easie Rules for the Dancing of Country-Dances, with the Tunes to each Dance. To which is added the Tunes of the most usual French Dances. And also other New and Pleasant English Tunes for the Trebe-Violin*, London, 1665, p. 52 (no. 61), F-Pn Musique, VM7 3564.

long-standing professional relationships.⁶⁶ They supplanted Italian singers in the regular performance of entertainments, with strong comic undertones, at the court and were often paid more than Lully himself. For example, the king gave Dupuis and La Barre 500 *livres* each for their performances in ballets performed in Versailles and Fontainebleau in 1664 while Lully received 300 *livres*.⁶⁷ In 1668, for a production of *George Dandin* in Versailles, Dupuis and Fonteaux de Cercamanan received precious jewellery, estimated at 400 *livres*, and other expensive costumes to wear during their performance.⁶⁸ The same year, Lully also performed a “mascarade royale” (*Carnaval*) in the Tuileries palace with decors from Carlo Vigarani.

II. Comic Legacy and Operatic Identity at the Inaugural Académie Royale de Musique

In June 1669, the creation of the Académie Royale de Musique in Paris put the definition of French opera to the test. Pierre Perrin (1620–1675), who held the royal privilege, was granted exclusive rights to write and stage operas in Paris.⁶⁹ Though he found some success as a librettist, his skills as a manager left much to be desired.⁷⁰ His collaboration with Robert Cambert (ca. 1628–77) exposed the logistical challenges of running a troupe—an essential factor in the successful launch of the ARM—alongside other crucial aspects of opera production.⁷¹ This was perceptible across different issues, which, as they accumulated, precipitated the downfall of Perrin’s operation. Crucially, one key problem involved the casting of a comic role; that of Béroé in the flagship production *Pomone*, premiered in 1671 for the Opéra’s inauguration,

The ARM’s administrative structure of the troupe, drawing from the model of the king’s musical ensembles (Chambre, Chapelle, and Écuries, all governed by the Menus-Plaisirs),

⁶⁶Loret mentioned them in his account of the *Leçon de Ténèbres* heard at the Église des Feuillants in 1662 (*Muze historique*, t. 4., p. 33, Letter of 31 March 1663).

⁶⁷La Gorce, *Lully*, p. 131. Paris, BnF, Manuscrits, Mélanges Colbert 269, f° 41.

⁶⁸F-Pn Manuscrits, Mélanges Colbert 269, f° 41.

⁶⁹The “*Lettres patentes*” (signed on 28 June 1669 at Saint-Germain-en-Laye) that described the ARM’s ownership were copied by Louis Durey de Noinville and Jean-Bernard Travenol (*Histoire du théâtre de l’Académie royale de musique en France depuis son établissement jusqu’à présent* [Paris: Duchesne, 1757]).

⁷⁰Perrin struggled to establish dependable financial business relationships, largely due to his tendency to align with unsuitable individuals or engage on unstable terms. Legal and financial turmoil directly followed the involvement of Alexandre de Rieux, known as Marquis Sourdéac and Laurent de Bersac de Fondant, known as Sieur de Champeron, who were supposed to provide funds for the launch of the Académie Royale de Musique. It involved the failure to secure a lease for a theatre (*Jeu de Paume du Becquet*), delays for the renovation of another (*Salle du Jeu de Paume de la Bouteille*) and, consequently, the creation of a debt whose amount and poor management ultimately forced Perrin out of business. The general confusion around all legal and financial arrangements (as reported in the *Mercur* in 1687 by Charles Nutter and Ernest Thoinan, *Les Origines de l’opéra français, d’après les minutes des notaires, les registres de la Conciergerie et les documents originaux conservés aux Archives nationales, à la Comédie-Française et dans diverses collections publiques et particulières* [Paris: Plon, 1886], p. 365) aggravated the attempts to fix the situation, such as a new partnership with Pierre Monier in 1670 (who took Sourdéac and Champeron to court in May 1670 after they failed to pay him), Jean de Granouillet, known as Sieur de Sablières (*intendant de la musique* for the duke of Orléans) on 8 August 1671, and Henri Guichard later that year.

⁷¹The study of the troupe under Perrin’s directorship is limited insofar that one musical score has survived (*Pomone*) while only librettos are accessible for the others. Thus a study addressing the specific skills (especially vocal skills and related musical semiotics) that could have been favoured through the development of their work is curtailed. However, the librettos, a handful of contemporaries’ testimonies, as well as the remains of various administrative sources, allow a peek into the fabric of the roles and the impact of the performers over them.

ought to be stable in order to reliably rehearse, perform, and ensure the commercial success of the establishment. The group of people assembled by Perrin and Cambert for the successful production of the *Pastorale d'Issy* (1659) and public rehearsal of *Ariane et Bacchus* (in 1661, just before the death of Mazarin) was an ephemeral formation and did not create an enduring sense of unity and stability. With the launch of the ARM, Perrin and Cambert had to start afresh.

The selection of singers for the cast of *Pomone* reflected the unstable and improvised nature of the enterprise. The finest performers in the Parisian region were already engaged at court and therefore not officially available for permanent contracts with the fledgling private Opera company—although the analysis of Lully's troupe in the following section will bring some nuance.⁷² To address this, Perrin and Cambert commissioned singer Pierre Monier to scour the provinces in search of fresh talents.⁷³ Beyond recruitment, Perrin also faced the challenge of maintaining cohesion—both among the singers themselves and in their relationship with the administration (which, in this case, meant Perrin and his collaborators).

Cambert, like Lully, had gained extensive experience at court before the launch of the Paris Opéra. This background, as with Lully's, honed his ability to identify and cultivate vocal talent with a discerning eye. In the obituary article that the *Mercur de France* published in April 1677, Cambert is indeed depicted as an artist who trained the best voices and who left them as a legacy to the Parisian audience many talents such as Mademoiselle Brigogne:

It is the same Cambert who was the first to use the beautiful voices that we still admire every day, and that Gascony gave to him; it is in his *Airs* that Mademoiselle Brigogne appeared the brightest, and it is through those that she charmed her spectators so much, to the extent that the nickname of *petite Climène* [from the role she played in *Les Peines et les plaisirs de l'amour*] remained.⁷⁴

Unfortunately, the cast for each of Perrin's and Cambert's productions cannot be fully established. *Pomone*'s cast is the most complete, followed by *Les Plaisirs et les peines de l'amour*

⁷²F-Pan, O1/16, fol. 94, March 1672, Versailles, "Privilege au St Perrin pour l'establissement d'une academie d'opera en musique et vers francois". The document is quoted by Marcelle Benoit, *Musiques de cours: Chapelle, Chambre, Écurie / Recueil de documents 1661-1733* (Paris: Picard, 1971), p. 37: "This [Academy] shall comprise whatever number and quality of people he sees fit—whom we shall choose and appoint on the basis of the report with which he provides us—to give performances in our presence when it pleases us of musical works that will be settings of either French or foreign works. [...] We permit [Lully] to give public performances of all the works he composes, even those staged in our presence, though he may not use in the [public] performance of the said works any musicians who are in our employ" (trans. Wood and Sadler, *French Baroque Opera*, pp. 7-8).

⁷³Nineteenth-century authors Charles Nutter and Ernest Thoinan relate Monier's task while offering a more detailed description of the singer in *Les Origines* (p. 118). Arthur Pougin (*Les vrais créateurs de l'Opéra français: Perrin et Cambert* [Paris: Charavay frères, 1881], p. 117) wrongly connect the task to find singers with Dominique Normandin de la Grille, a singer for the *Musique du Roi* and a friend of Perrin who, during this period, was in prison (F-Pan, O1/14, fol. 340, Registre du Secrétaire du Roi).

⁷⁴*Mercur de France* (April 1677), pp. 15–18: "C'est ce même Cambert qui a fait chanter le premier les belles Voix que nous admirons tous les jours, et que la Gasconne lui avait fournies; c'est dans ses *Airs* que Mademoiselle Brigogne a paru avec le plus d'éclat, et c'est par eux qu'elle a tellement charmé tous ses Auditeurs, que le nom de la petite Climène lui en est demeuré."

Table 1: Female singers hired at the Académie under the successive directions of Perrin and Lully

Name	Other spellings	Dates	Origin	Official enrolment at the ARM
Catherine Suptille		b.1651-a.1671		1669-71
Marotte Labadoys		b.1652-a.1672		1669-71
Marie Aubry		ca.1646-1704		1671; 1674-84
Mlle La Gaura		b.1652-a.1670		1669
Marie-Madeleine	Brie?	ca.1651-a.1695		1671-80
Brigogne				
Marie-Madeleine		ca.1650-1717		1670-73
Jossier, known as Cartilly				
Marie Verier	Du Verdier, Duverdier	ca.1620-a.1714		1675-80
Mlle Saint-Christophe	Saint-Christophe	ca.1625-a.1683		1675-82
Saint-Christophe				
Marie Le Rochois	Rochehouai, Rochois, Rochoix, Rochoüas, Rochoys	ca.1661-8 Oct 1728	Region of Bayeux	1679-97
Marie-Louise Moreau [L.]	Louison, Moreau l'aînée	b.1661-a.1713	Paris	1680-92
Françoise Moreau [c.]	Fanchon, Mareau la cadette, Morlan	ca.1668-3 Nov 1754	Paris	1682-1702
Marie-Louise Desmatins	Demathin, Démâtins, Des Matains, Desmâtins	b.1665-20 Apr 1708	Probably Parisian region	1682-1707

(1672, libretto by Gabriel Gilbert, music by Cambert).⁷⁵ From the limited historical evidence available on the female singers employed by Perrin, one significant challenge stands out in the distribution of roles—particularly in relation to the performance of comedy on stage. The casting of Pomone’s title role and the comic role of Béroé became a major point of contention between the directors and Catherine Suptille, highlighting the difficulties in balancing artistic expectations and theatrical conventions within the nascent ARM.⁷⁶

Before the launch of the Académie Royale de Musique, Suptille had already performed the leading role in the revival of *Ariane, ou le mariage de Bacchus* (1669–70). Logically, she should have been assigned Pomone, the goddess of fruits, which was the leading female character in Perrin’s new production. This role, however, was given to Marie-Madeleine Jossier, known as Cartilly (ca. 1650–1717), while Suptille ended up with a secondary role, that of Béroé.

Béroé’s character, Pomone’s old nanny, closely parallels other traditional comic characters and, in particular, the Italian *comedia dell’arte* tradition, which relied heavily on stock characters, physical comedy, and exaggerated scenarios to entertain audiences. Older female characters—often portrayed as nannies, maids, or meddling matrons—were known as *vecchie*. These roles were typically played by male actors, a practice rooted in the era’s theatrical conventions. The cross-dressing element, staple of entertainment, amplified the absurdity of the characters through exaggerated costumes, mannerisms, and vocal affectations. In *commedia* scenarios, the nanny or *vecchia* might serve as a confidante, a comic obstacle, or a parody of maternal authority. For example, she could be tasked with guarding a young lover (*innamorata*) only to be outwitted by the clever servant or suitor. Her cross-dressed portrayal added a layer of irony—her authority undermined not just by her bumbling nature but by the audience’s awareness of the male performer beneath the disguise. Jean-François Lattarico has shown how these roles, such as the model of the nymphomaniac old nursemaid inherited from erudite comedies of the Renaissance, infiltrated 1640s Italian operas, alongside a wide range of other characters, so as to introduce more vocal diversity.⁷⁷

Cambert and Perrin had previously employed comic roles as a means of creating functional antagonists within the diegesis. However, they had largely assigned such roles to grotesque male figures or mythological creatures—such as the Faun in *Les Peines et les Plaisirs de l’Amour*, also used in *Pomone*—whose physical oddities and misplaced romantic aspirations invited laughter without challenging conventional gender norms. The decision to instead cast a female character and performer in a comedic role marked a departure from this approach, inevitably provoking resistance and controversy.

⁷⁵ *Les Amours de Diane et d’Endymion* (1671, libretto by Henry Guichard, music by Jean Granouillet de Sablière) has only three identifiable names, and *Ariane, ou le mariage de Bacchus* (rehearsed in public in 1661 then again in 1669–70, libretto by Perrin, music by Cambert) only one. Earlier works such as *La mort d’Adonis* (1659?, libretto by Perrin, music by Jean-Baptiste Boisset) and the *Pastorale d’Isy* (1659, libretto by Perrin, music by Cambert), which Prunières believed set a precedent for a French opera understood as national style, left no record of their respective casts. See Prunières, *L’Opéra italien*, p. 347–8.

⁷⁶ Nutter and Thoinan, *Les Origines*, p. 134: “Pendant les répétitions de *Pomone*, Catherine Suptille avait paru insuffisante, et on lui avait retiré son rôle sans vouloir la payer. Elle intenta, elle aussi, un procès à Sourdéac et Champeron, et ce n’est qu’après bien des alternatives que ce procès se termina en mars 1671.”

⁷⁷ Jean-François Lattarico, “La voix du chanteur italien au XVIe siècle. De la prescription à la perception”, in *Les sons du théâtre : Angleterre et France (XVIe-XVIIIe siècle). Éléments d’une histoire de l’écoute* (Presses universitaires de Rennes, 2013), p. 7.

In a long letter allegedly written by Catherine Suptille, as reported by nineteenth-century historians Nutter and Thoinan (the validity of which is not fully verifiable), the female singer objected vigorously to that decision:

It happened that Marotte Labadoys, who is relatively well-known in society and in particular by Cambert, told me that she gave two hundred and fifty *livres* from her pension to Cambert, which is why the first role, which I was owed, was not assigned to me, since I did not want to give Cambert the same amount from my pension, which meant that he gave me a role that is usually executed in Italian opera by men disguised as nannies only; his insolence goes as far as saying that I have a deformed face and that I am not able to sing a tender roles, what is more is that he says that my voice is weak because of my pregnancy, which is a proof of a great ignorance for which I am ready to take the matter in front of Monsieur De Nyel, the first valet of the king, Dambruys and Molière, musicians who have heard and seen me singing the first role in the work *Ariane*, which makes for the whole plot of the play, people who after they have seen me performed have admitted out loud in front of the assembly that I was the only one capable to execute this role; and that without me the opera would not be worth being heard, and have offered me to sing it in front of all the experts of Paris that can be chosen as referees. I will expose Cambert's mistake and show that I have the capacity now as before to sing that role. It is not that I have the ambition to sing all the first roles, but only that I want to show those who are invested in operas [probably Perrin and Cambert] that when they speak about the last role I was assigned in *Pomone*, saying that I will not sing it nor any other, and that I won't be part of their opera, and that I only had to retire, I am forced to conclude against them that they have to pay me the pension they promised me on paper and have to compensate me for the sum of two thousands *livres* which they required from me through said treaty since they indicated with their defences that I would have needed to give back my role in order to not be part of said Opera.⁷⁸

Suptille openly criticised the role of Béroé as “usually executed in Italian operas by men

⁷⁸ Archives de la Comédie-Française transcribed by Nutter and Thoinan, *Les Origines*, pp. 134-136 (without any call number): “Est arrivé que la nommée Marotte Labadoys qui est assez connue dans le monde et particulièrement du dit Cambert, laquelle m'a dit qu'elle donnait à perdre au dit Cambert sur sa pension la somme de deux cent cinquante livres, ce qui a été cause qu'il ne m'a pas été donné le premier rôle qui m'était dû parce que je n'ai pas voulu adhérer à lui en accorder autant sur ma pension, ce qui a fait qu'il m'a donné un rôle qui n'est exécuté d'ordinaire dans les opéras d'Italie que par un homme déguisé en nourrice, et comme son insolence va jusqu'à dire que j'ai le visage difforme et que je ne suis pas capable de chanter un rôle tendre d'autant qu'il dit que ma voix est affaiblie à cause de ma grossesse, ce qui est une preuve très grande de son ignorance, laquelle je suis prête à faire voir devant Monsieur De Nyel, premier valet de chambre du Roy, les sieurs Dambruy et Molière, musiciens qui m'ont ouïe et vue chanter le premier rôle et faire mon personnage dans la pièce d'*Ariane*, qui fait tout le sujet de la pièce, lesquels après me l'avoir vu représenter ont avoué et dit hautement devant l'assemblée qu'il n'y avait que moi au monde capable d'exécuter ce rôle; et que sans moi l'opéra ne vaudrait pas la peine d'être entendu, et m'offre à le chanter présentement devant les plus experts de Paris qu'on pourra choisir pour arbitres. Et ferai voir l'ânerie de Cambert en ce rencontre, et que j'ai autant de capacité présentement que j'avais en ce temps-là pour le chanter. Ce n'est pas pour ambitionner tous les premiers rôles ce que j'en fais, mais seulement pour faire voir que les dits intéressés aux opéras ne devaient pas, lorsque parlant du dernier rôle qui m'a été donné dans la seconde pièce nommée *Pomone*, dire que je ne chanterais ni celui-là, ni un autre, et que je ne serais plus de leur opéra, et que je n'avais qu'à me retirer, ce qui m'oblige de conclure à l'encontre d'eux à ce qu'ils aient à me payer la pension à quoi ils sont obligés par leur écrit et me dédommager de la somme de deux mille livres à laquelle ils m'ont obligée par le dit traité puisqu'ils m'ont fait signifier par leurs défenses que j'eusse à rendre mon rôle pour ne plus être du dit Opéra.”

disguised as nannies only”. Instead, she reclaimed for herself the role of Pomone, a soft and gentle goddess, suggesting that it was identical in nature to that of Ariane. Indeed, Béroé—an old nanny whose extinguished passion is revived by the god Vertumne—was ill-suited for her and the French theatrical tradition. Contrary to its Italian counterpart, French spoken theatre in the seventeenth-century tended to avoid the masculine and comic “confidants et nourrices” to feminine and more serious “confidentes et caractères”.⁷⁹

In *Pomone*, Béroé is performed by a woman, Suptille. However, the role of Vertumne—sung by the *haute-contre* Bernard Clédière (b. 1640–ca. 1712)—“transforms” himself as the nanny Béroé in an attempt to seduce the goddess Pomone. This intricate narrative, with layered levels of codified comic effects, relied on a challenging equilibrium in terms of acting and voice for both performers in charge of Vertumne and Béroé. By using a woman and a man to perform the same character, the authors nodded to the Italian origins of the comic old nurse, a theatrical lineage that may have fuelled Suptille’s suspicions about being cast in the role.

Given the lack of additional sources on this specific case, the interpretation of this disagreement about the distribution of roles between the singer and the Académie’s administration can only be a matter of inference and speculation. It could be that the pool of talents among women was small and that such important roles were difficult to fulfil.⁸⁰ It could also be an indication of a broader lack of cohesion and coordination within the troupe, between performers, authors, and administration.

Suptille petitioned Perrin and Cambert for the chance to prove she was capable of performing roles of greater poetic significance than the one she had been assigned. She flatly rejected the composer’s criticisms—particularly the claims regarding her “deformed” face and “weak” voice, which Cambert allegedly attributed as the result of her pregnancy. The historians Nutter and Thoinan added to that testimony that Suptille later decided to sue Sourdéac and Champeron, with the trial concluding in 1671.⁸¹

The specific complaint made by Suptille, regarding her disapproval of performing the secondary role of Béroé and her request to assume the leading female role, sheds light on several other aspects. Firstly, it underscores the recognition within the troupe of a hierarchical structure between roles, partly influenced by the ethos and emotional range associated with each character. In the case of Béroé, the comedic aspect of both the female role and the male cross-dressing version, drawing from Italian practices, played a significant role in this ranking. At that point in time, when the ARM had few employees in its troupe but an abundance of characters, many singers could perform several roles of different importance. Nevertheless, Suptille’s complaint makes clear that not all roles were equal, and even if not in terms of salary, but certainly in terms of prestige and public recognition. The comedic element of Béroé directly contributed to her lower rank among the other characters, which, in turn, led to Suptille’s own sense of degradation.

This hypothesis is supported by the fact that Béroé, despite being secondary in social status among the other plot characters, is actually challenging vocally, and is given ample exposure

⁷⁹Virginia Scott, “Conniving Women and Superannuated Coquettes: “Travestis” and “Caractères” in the Early Modern French Theatre”, *Early Theatre* 15, no. 1 (2012), p. 191.

⁸⁰This is the hypothesis made by Nutter and Thoinan (*Les Origines*, p. 134) who wrote that Suptille’s talents “appeared to be insufficient” but do not provide any source to substantiate their thesis.

⁸¹Nutter and Thoinan, *Les Origines*, p. 134.

throughout the opera. Therefore, it does not represent a simpler role than that of Pomone in any way. In fact, for two-thirds of the second act, the nanny becomes the central figure of the plot. She explains her love for Vertumne (II, 1), suffers his rejection (II, 2), and endures the presence and effects of various magical spells. First with Vertumne who, transformed into a dragon, pretends that he will devour her (II, 4). Then against twelve ghosts, performed by dancers, who harass her (II, 5) until she is rescued and carried away by the God of the Gardens. All these twists give way to three monologues (sc. 1, 4, and 5), in addition to one long dialogue with Vertumne (sc. 3), during which Béroé displays a large array of vocal effects. From the introduction of the second act, during which her complaint is highlighted by conjunct movements—often melismatic, within a narrow vocal range—the following monologue (II, 4) offers a sharp contrast. Cambert uses disjunct intervals and a simpler rhythmic pattern, with semiquavers to drive the expression of Béroé’s desolation (with the exception of the line “Et ne puis mourir”, which creates variety and even, perhaps, a comic relief). Moreover, Béroé’s voice blends with Pomone and her sister Flore’s at the start of the opera (I, 2) during a trio where the goddess of fruits rejects Vertumne’s advances while Flore praises him, and Béroé condemns him. The melodic profiles for each character are the same, which creates an impression of likeness between them, even though they have different social ranks. Of course, the comic dimension of Béroé’s character also contributes to this impression.

Secondly, Suptille’s complaint suggests that performers had some leeway to contest the directors’ authority if the roles they were assigned did not match their expectations or the skills for which they had been originally employed. On that point, it is necessary to recall Cambert’s alleged comment that is reported in Suptille’s complaint by Nutter and Thoinan. If her voice was ever so “weak”, how could she have performed this character which, all in all, seems more challenging than the one of Pomone? Whether Cambert’s criticism was fabricated or not, it does not align with the final decision regarding the distribution of roles (specifically requesting Suptille’s performance, rather than another singer). From that perspective, it might be possible that the variety of effects expected from Béroé also repelled or discouraged the singer. If so, Suptille’s request to take up the title role of Pomone may have represented an attempt to avoid the musical challenge represented by Béroé, something that, if she were to fail during the performance, could have indeed damaged her social reputation and legitimacy in the troupe.

Both Perrin and Cambert showed an exceptional degree of resilience by adapting quickly to their material constraints. *Pomone* enjoyed great success with the public: the opera was performed more than seventy times over eight months, with a seat in the *parterre* costing half a *louis d’or*.⁸² Jacques-Gabriel Prod’homme and Theodore Barker have pointed out that “the attendance was such that clashes took place between the citizens and the pages, lackeys and men in livery who sought to enter in the train of their masters, as they did at other spectacles”.⁸³ Ultimately, a royal ordinance was promulgated in order to prevent people from entering the ARM gratis. Yet, sustainable profits did not accumulate. Ultimately, Perrin’s poor management of the Académie precipitated his exit from the institution, in favour of Lully.

III. The Shape of French Opera Under Lully’s Directorship (1672–87)

⁸² Albert Borowitz, “Lully and the Death of Cambert”, *Legal Studies Forum* 29, no. 2 (2005), p. 900.

⁸³ Jacques-Gabriel Prod’homme and Theodore Barker, “Two Hundred and Fifty Years of the Opéra (1669–1919)”, *The Musical Quarterly* 5, no. 4 (1919): 516.

Unlike the turbulent beginnings of Perrin and Cambert, Jean-Baptiste Lully's takeover of the Académie Royale de Musique in March 1672 unfolded under far more controlled conditions. Lully's managerial ingenuity, personal ambition, and undeniable artistic talent enabled him to consolidate and stabilise the institution with remarkable speed.⁸⁴ This sense of control extended to every aspect of the enterprise—including his creative partnership with librettist Philippe Quinault. Though central to the success of Lully's *tragédies en musique*, the collaboration was notably asymmetrical, further reinforcing Lully's authority over the institution.⁸⁵ Lully's directorship exerted influence not only over the structural and managerial organisation of the troupe but also over the very content of the plots that underpinned his *tragédies en musique*.

His earlier experience at court had already taught him the value of comic relief—not merely as entertainment, but as a strategic tool in advancing his career. The blend of comic choreography and operatic convention continued into Lully's works. The operatic characters created under his leadership were closely shaped around the skills and stage personas of the available performers, including their capacity for comic performance. In this way, Lully's casting decisions reveal a deliberate strategy of authority-building, firmly rooted in the politics of typecasting—an issue already laid bare in the *Pomone* controversy with Suptille.

Lully's strategic acumen was particularly evident in his selection of singers. An analysis of his casts—even before he officially took over the ARM up until 1682, at which point the court was formally transferred to Versailles and full operatic productions became logistically rarer—reveals a deliberate and tactical approach. Certain performers from the Musique du Roi, though formally tied to royal service, were regularly redeployed by Lully to fulfil specific role types, especially in court performances—whether revivals or, more rarely, premieres—but not only. A notable example is the 1675 Parisian premiere of *Thésée* at the ARM, then situated in the Palais-Royal, an opera that eventually became one of Lully's most enduring successes, whose cast was largely drawn from the Musique du Roi. This pattern marked a significant departure from Perrin's earlier model, and reflected either Lully's superior access to royal networks, or simply his greater audacity in bending institutional boundaries—perhaps both.

The most prominent cases of singers affiliated to the Musique du Roi who sang in Lully's operas can be classed in three different categories. The first one encompassed the *basses-tailles*

⁸⁴After he gained the control of the Opéra, Lully even received additional powers with an ordinance, signed by Louis Colbert, which made him forbid actors to use more than two singers and six instrumentalists in performances they could give outside of the Opéra: "His Majesty expressly forbids all troupes of actors, French or foreign, established or to be established hereafter in the fair city of Paris, to use any external musicians, nor a larger number of instrumentalists for the entr'actes, nor any dancers, nor any orchestra, on pain of punishment for disobedience. His Majesty wishes that the present ordinance be notified to the leaders of such troupes, at the behest of the said Lully, in order that they be made aware of it; His Majesty enjoining him to inform him of any contraventions of this ordinance." (F-Pan, O1/17, f. 72: 'Ordonnance portant défenses aux comédiens' [22 April 1673].)

⁸⁵Lully's authority over Quinault is mentioned by Banducci ("Acteurs and Actrices as Muses", §11.4) and La Gorce (*Lully*, 583). This point of view is not equally shared among scholars. Buford Norman, for example, argues in *Quinault, librettiste de Lully: le poète des grâces*, that Quinault's influence over Lully might have been "considerable" (Mardaga, 2001, 18). However, Norman's argument is based on an intuition only: the sole fact that the genre of *tragédie en musique* was born at the moment when Lully collaborated with Quinault is no clear indicator of any creative balance between the two artists.

Jean Gaye (ca. 1640–5 April 1701) and Antoine I Morel (b. 1652–1711), who will be discussed later, and the *basse-contre* Jacques Godonesche (b. 1654–November 1711). All three singers were granted mature males figures (kings, deities) and key male secondary roles (confidants, mythological creatures). A second category was represented by female singers, including Anne Fonteaux de Cercamanan (b. 1640–a. 1719), who had been involved in Lully's musical ventures prior to his acquisition of the ARM, and Mademoiselle Bony (b. 1657–a. 1682). In Lully's operas, they specialised in secondary female roles that, while not central, played a crucial part in driving the plot forward. Much like Gaye and Morel, their characters typically served as influential supporting figures, endowed with either useful powers or significant social standing. Occasionally, Lully would also ask additional female talents from the Musique du Roi for other roles; for example, Marguerite Pièche the elder (23 September 1648–a. 1718) regularly performed secondary roles often much smaller in importance and lighter in tone.

Finally, a third group encompassed more diverse talents. It gathered François Langeais (b. 1651–1682), Philippe Le Roy de Beaumont (b. 1645–October 1704), Dominique de Normandin, known as La Grille (ca. 1645–8 November 1717), Jean Borel, known as Miracle (1646–16 November 1728) and Bernard Clédière (b. 1640–ca. 1712). Their tessitura, situated between *haute-contre* and *taille*, allowed them to exploit the upper register of their voices with flexibility. Clédière and Miracle started at the ARM before eventually joining the Musique du Roi in 1675 and 1678 respectively, more specifically the Chapelle Royale where their high tessitura would have been well suited to the demands of sacred music. Alternatively, the vocal colour of that same tessitura could be used to create nuanced comedic effects. In an operatic context, however, the same vocal colour lent itself equally well to refined comic nuance. All these singers were frequently cast in secondary roles—mostly allegorical in nature—with occasional parts that drew heavily from theatrical comic traditions.

The *haute-contre* Clédière, originally recruited by Pierre Perrin, was among the first singers to take on comic parts while also portraying more conventional masculine leads and assisting deities; indeed, he was the one playing Vertumne in *Pomone*, the god who used different disguises to seduce the female lead character, including that of the comic nanny Béroé. For the creation and first revival of *Cadmus et Hermione*, Clédière also played the roles of L'Envie (Greed) and La Nourrice (Hermione's Nanny), the latter building on the same theatrical tradition of Béroé. In a 1678 reprisal of the same opera, after Clédière started his employment at the Musique du Roi (1675), Lully reassigned him different parts (*Le Soleil, un Prince Tyrien*) while transferring the roles he had originated to Philippe Le Roy de Beaumont. This redistribution clarified Clédière's operatic repertoire and reinforced Beaumont's comedic identity, while underscoring the composer's wish to maintain the original comic relief. Spectators could still easily identify and anticipate the presence and function of comedic roles.

The enduring presence of *taille* singers within the ARM's troupe, albeit placed at the lowest ranked salary within the ARM's troupe, highlights Lully's deliberate choice to integrate and keep comic elements into his operas. The roles they played were potentially relevant from a dramaturgical and narrative perspectives; importantly, the combination of a specific male tessitura with secondary roles ensured a consistent and recognisable comedic presence on stage that blended with the trajectory of these singers' careers.

Table 2: Modelisation of the Académie Royale de Musique's troupe as described by the 1713 Règlement

Tessiture	Sex	Description of the title	Position in the hierarchy	Salary (in livres)
Basse-taille	M	First actor	'First Subject' or actor 'in chief'	1500
Haute-contre	M	First actor	'First Subject' or actor 'in chief'	1500
	F	First actress	'First Subject' or actor 'in chief'	1500
Basse-taille	M	Second actor	First understudy	1200
Haute-contre	M	Second actor	First understudy	1200
	F	Second actress	First understudy	1200
	M	Third actor	Second understudy or double	1000
Haute-contre	M	Third actor	Second understudy or double	1000
	F	Third actress	Second understudy or double	1000
	F	Fourth actress	–	900
	F	Fifth actress	–	800
	F	Sixth actress	–	700
	Taille	M	First actor	–
Taille	M	Second actor	–	600

This argument is reinforced by the fact that Langeais, Beaumont, La Grille, Clédière, and Miracle were not the only singers with mid-to-high tessituras related to the Musique du Roi whom Lully required for his productions. The pool of talents at the court, from which the composer occasionally borrowed also included Michel Bernard (ca. 1650–1713), Jolain (b. 1654–a. 1707), Michel Alexis, known as La Forêt (b. 1650–a. 1687), and Léonore Gingant *le cadet* (b. 1645–a. 1713). Whether such performers were inherently rare or the remuneration insufficient to encourage ARM singers to cultivate this tessitura presents a nuanced, cyclical dilemma. Regardless of which issue came first, the fact is that Lully persevered in looking for adequate performers capable of fulfilling these more comic-oriented roles, associated with that particular quality of voice, instead of cutting them from his scores—and therefore from the cast.

The presence of these singers and the roles they played, some of them explicitly comic, echoes a broader rule: *tragédies en musique* were not aesthetically “pure”. They sometimes displayed comic elements in the text, music, acting, or dance—or a combination of these—and were not always sticking to a tragic *ethos* throughout the plot. Lully, like Perrin and Cambert before him, did not step into the ARM business with a ready-made operatic template. Instead of being a straightforward process, the elaboration of the genre witnessed numerous attempts to experiment with diverse material, some of which included Italian songs, comic register, non-linear and parallel love stories.

In Quinault's libretto of *Cadmus et Hermione* (1673), the heroine is abducted by the giant Draco, who intends to force her into marriage. Cadmus, undeterred by the mortal danger, resolves to rescue her—even if it costs him his life. Guarding the giant's domain is a fearsome

dragon that Cadmus must first defeat. Two comic figures lighten the dramatic tension: Arbas, Cadmus's servant, flees in terror at the sight of the dragon, but once Cadmus departs in search of Hermione, he boastfully claims to have slain the beast himself. He then declares his love to Charité (a mythological grace and one of Hermione's two confidants), with such breezy indifference that his casual posture offers a stark—and humorous—counterpoint to Cadmus's noble devotion. Hermione's old nurse, in line with the tradition of cross-dressing comic roles already discussed, gives voice to jealousy in a manner that is exaggerated and ridiculous rather than bitter or threatening. After that, two dancers, appearing as Africans, begin their elegant tribute to Hermione while four hulking giants burst in, uninvited—most likely stomping about with comic clumsiness.⁸⁶

Archival records of the early casts do not reveal who performed the role of Arbas. However, the name of Antoine Morel, *basse-taille* employed at the Musique du Roi, appears in later documents for the first revival of the opera in 1678. The same singer performed the comic roles of Caron and Straton in *Alceste*, discussed below. In later years, all three roles remained paired in the repertoire assigned to Jean Dun père (b. 1668–1745). From that basis, it is likely that Morel was part of *Cadmus et Hermione*'s original cast, playing Arbas.⁸⁷ By contrast, we know for certain that Clédière played the cross-dressed comic nurse—another role consistent with the comic repertoire he previously performed—while Marie-Madeleine Jossier (known as Cartilly), the same performer whose appointment to the title role in *Pomone* had sparked Catherine Suptille's protest, was cast as Charité, a non-comic and lyrically poised character. This distribution suggests that Lully and Quinault carefully aligned performers' known strengths and stage personae with the demands of each role: assigning Clédière to parts that drew on his established comic identity, while reserving the more dignified role of Charité for Jossier instead of any other female singer.

Alceste also preserved traces of Venetian opera in its inclusion of comic characters and light-hearted servant subplots. Opening the Act IV, Caron, surrounded by comically plaintive souls ("Shadows"), insists upon a gratuity before his ferry can carry anyone across the River Styx. Lully's comic touch also reappears in the final *divertissement* (Act V, scene 6) with bumpkin herdsmen surrounding Straton. Likewise, *Thésée* features an entertaining secondary storyline, though it involves higher-ranking characters who carry themselves with greater propriety. While some playful dialogue did scandalise critics, the most obvious comic moment lies in the Act II *divertissement*, with its song and dance for a group of doddering old men.

On the matter of blending different musical, poetic, and stylistic features, the early *tragédies* in particular, *Cadmus et Hermione*, *Alceste* and *Thésée*, stand out in the Lullian repertoire because of the robust quarrels they sparked. Indeed contemporaries were not always receptive to Lully's deliberate blurring of aesthetic boundaries. Many saw the comic detours and occasionally tangled subplots as a flagrant snub to the poetic decorum that ruled seventeenth-century French spoken theatre. For instance, Charles Le Marquetel de Saint-Denis, known as the Seigneur de Saint-Évremond (1614–1703), criticised the lack of etiquette (*bienséance*) and

⁸⁶Rebecca Harris-Warrick, "La danse dans *Cadmus et Hermione*", in Jane Duron, ed., *Cadmus et Hermione de Jean-Baptiste Lully et Philippe Quinault: Livret, études et commentaires*, Wavre: Mardaga, 2008, p. 239–41.

⁸⁷This thesis is reinforced by the fact that Morel was no debutant in matters of comedy; in the premiere of *Les Amants Magnifiques* (1670), the singer played one of the two comic Satyres, who, in the third intermezzo, take comfort in wine after being turned down by the shepherdess Caliste.

verisimilitude for *Cadmus et Hermione* (1673), the first of Lully's *tragédies*.⁸⁸ Detractors of *Alceste* addressed the same issues through the publication of pamphlets against and in favour of the opera.⁸⁹ It was criticised for its mix of buffoonery with tragedy, which added jarring comic elements out of place in this tragic subject.

Thésée is a great case in point in Lully's strategic approach to casting and character construction, composing with specific singers in mind to achieve his goals. Dorine, confidant of the furious Médée, central to the opera's narrative, is the only secondary-ranked roles played by a female singer in this production. From a strictly aesthetic standpoint, her prominence sits somewhat awkwardly within the tragic decorum of a *tragédie en musique*. Indeed, despite her social rank, she enjoys great exposure on stage, notably with a monologue (Act II, scene 5) and a romantic sub-plot involving Arcas (recalled in Act II, scene 4), and is rather influential over the general course of actions. Her stage presence and expressive autonomy might more naturally belong to the *pastorale* tradition, to which *Pomone* belongs, where secondary characters routinely enjoy solo scenes. In fact, traces of this earlier operatic language remain in Dorine's comic inflections in Act II, scene 1—features that recall the lingering type of Béroé, whose grotesque comic presence seems to haunt the transition between *pastorale* and *tragédie* at the ARM. Yet from a performer-centred perspective, the rationale becomes clearer. Dorine's role appears to have been specifically designed for Anne de Beaucreux (b. 1656–ca. 1680), a singer who, while never enjoying the renown of Marie Aubry or Marie Le Rochois, seems to have earned Lully's trust and artistic confidence.⁹⁰ Despite the scarcity of historical sources surrounding the production, Beaucreux's involvement in the troupe—confirmed by her presence in legal records and period press—suggests a dependable figure within the ensemble.⁹¹ Her suitability for such a role likely justified Dorine's exceptional visibility. The part would later be assigned to several other rising talents across the following decades, including Miss Ferdinand la cadette (1677, 1678), Louise-Élisabeth Heusé (1707, 1708), Anne Mignier (1720, 1729), and Louise Jacquet (1744), underscoring its role as a vehicle for showcasing promising performers.

But the presence of comic elements in Lully's operas was not limited to his early *tragédies*. It perdured after *Thésée*, the turning point after which Lully supposedly avoided “popular” and overtly comic material.⁹² Madame de Sévigné famously commented that this shift was made “to erase Venice”.⁹³ It may be relatively straightforward to distinguish works that fall outside the genre of *tragédie en musique*, but identifying which of Lully's *tragédies* contain a

⁸⁸ *Nouvelles oeuvres mêlées de M. de Saint-Évremond*, ed. Abbé François Raguenet (Paris: Vve de C. Barbin, 1700), p. 36.

⁸⁹ Charles Perrault, the first collaborator of Minister Colbert within the Petite Académie which followed closely all forms of art production and advised the king, a member of the Académie Française, and General Controller of the Buildings, Gardens, Arts and Manufactures of the King, wrote a vigorous and influential defence of *Alceste* (*Critique de l'opéra, ou Examen de la tragédie intitulée Alceste, ou le Triomphe d'Alcide* [Paris, 16 July 1674]).

⁹⁰ As in the case of Marie Aubry, Anne de Beaucreux was involved in the trial opposing Guichard and Lully (*Requête d'Henry Guichard, où l'on va établir l'innocence et la justification du suppliant*, [1675–1676], F-Pn, f. Fm 7207–8; *Mercur galant* [Paris], February 1680, III, 261–2).

⁹¹ Claude and François Parfaict, *Histoire de l'Académie royale de Musique, depuis son établissement jusqu'à présent* (1741), t. I, p. 30.

⁹² Abbé Dubos, *Réflexions critiques sur la Poésie et la Peinture* (Paris: Jean Mariette, 1719), vol. 1, p. 178, as cited by Manuel Couvreur in *Jean-Baptiste Lully. Musique et dramaturgie au service du prince* (Marc Vokar, 1992), p. 292.

⁹³ Letter of 24 November 1673, cited in Couvreur, *Lully*, p. 291.

notable comic dimension is a far more nuanced task. This deflection of comic material into the *divertissements* would become increasingly common in the next generation of opera composers, but examples already appear in Lully's own works after *Thésée*, such as the palace of the river god Sangar in *Atys* (Act IV), and the chorus of shivering mortals in *Isis* (Act IV). Even within the high stakes of mythological tragedy, comic relief was not an embellishment, but a structural necessity—woven into the fabric of Lully's vision for a hybrid operatic form.

The clearest case appears in *Psyché*, where the final *divertissement* features Momus, a chorus of Polichinelles, and a drunken Bacchus, leaving no doubt as to its comic intent. Based on the 1671 *tragédie-ballet* of the same name, *Psyché* (1678) underwent significant reworking to become a *tragédie en musique*. The spoken dialogue was reimaged and fully set to music, while the original *intermèdes* were expanded into fully fledged *divertissements*. Yet, despite this operatic makeover—and despite following the more serious opera productions of *Atys* (1676) and *Isis* (1677)—*Psyché* retained a remarkable number of comic characters, gestures, and scenes, outpacing even *Thésée* in this regard. It is not possible to know for certain why these buffoons were neither cut nor toned down in the 1678 ARM production. Perhaps, as Harris-Warrick argues, the relegation of humour to the *divertissements* made it more acceptable to audiences and critics alike.⁹⁴ But, again, its mere presence strongly suggests that the opposition to comic elements was simply less entrenched than what is commonly assumed in the existing scholarship on French early modern opera. In any case, *Psyché* delivers its humour in two strikingly different episodes: in Act II, where dancing Cyclopes bring a grotesque touch to Vulcan's forge, and in the jubilant ending, where Jupiter assembles a riotously incongruous guest list for the celestial wedding banquet. This *gigue finale* capitalised on expressive language of exaggerated motion and comic timing, functioning as both catharsis and commentary within the operatic frame.

In *Persée* (premiered on 18 April 1682), Lully and Quinault chose to attribute comic traits to the monstrous role of Méduse. At this time, Lully and Quinault had accustomed their audience to associating one leading performer (generally female) with the expression of power and magic, using a long baton or staff (*baguette*) as a theatrical accessory. In *Persée*, however, the authors disrupted that pattern. Méduse, the antique figure that petrifies people who look at her, was assigned to a male *taille*, Claude Desvoyes (ca. 1639–November 1709); by doing so, Lully reconnected with the tradition of ugly and comic cross-dressing roles. The choice cannot be solely explained using aesthetic terms, disconnected from the study of the performers. Indeed, in 1682, Lully had to deal with a greater number of female leader soloists than usual. He could hardly dismiss the singers already placed at the top of the troupe hierarchy, Marie Aubry and Mademoiselle Saint-Christophe, who performed Andromède and Cassiopée respectively. At the same time, the role of Mérope is evidently curated so as to expose the talents of Lully's new and rising star, Marie Le Rochois. Her fantastic singing and acting skills are highlighted in not less than three monologues: “Ah! Je garderai bien mon cœur” (Act I, scene 3), “Hélas! Il va périr! Dois-je en trembler?” (Act II, scene 4), and “Ô mort, venez finir mon destin déplorable” (Act V, scene 1). By linking comic relief to the cross-dressed role Méduse, rather than casting a woman in the part, Lully emphasised the functionality of that character and its literary lineage, grounded in Ovid's *Metamorphoses*, while also sidestepping the kind

⁹⁴Harris-Warrick, *Dance and drama*, 157.

of conflict provoked by the casting of Béroé.

Claims that Lully turned his back on comic material after *Thésée* also tend to overlook the long afterlife of his early work, including *ballets*, *comédies-ballets*, and *tragédies en musique*, which remained staples of the repertory well into the eighteenth century—comic scenes and all. It underscored the permanence of comedy on the ARM stage even when the *tragédie en musique* gained in theory greater poetic cohesion. *La Grotte de Versailles*, *Pourceaugnac*, and *Le Carnaval*, for example, among Lully's light-hearted pieces originally produced for the court, remained highly popular and were regularly reprised after his death at the ARM. *Cadmus et Hermione* was revived eight times between its 1673 premiere and 1737, with the role of the cross-dressed nurse, always sung by a man, consistently preserved. In *Alceste*, the *basso buffo* Charon—forever with his hand out for bribes—was never cut. Nor were the doddering old men of *Thésée*, which saw no fewer than eleven revivals, the last as late as 1779. These moments of humour may occupy only a sliver of the operas' total duration and are certainly more restrained than the comic interludes of Venetian opera. Yet their uninterrupted presence on the stage of the Opéra suggests that Parisian audiences were long accustomed to a more layered vision of Lully's genre—one in which grandeur and wit could comfortably coexist.

That the works of a deceased composer would continue to be performed regularly for decades marked a genuine novelty. The repeated revivals of Lully's operas introduced—for the first time in the history of French opera—the notion of a musical canon: a repertoire that came to function as a cultural touchstone, shaping collective memory, defining standards of taste, and serving as a reference point for both audiences and performers alike.⁹⁵ This idea is made strikingly clear in Jean-Louis Le Cerf de La Viéville's *Comparaison de la Musique italienne et de la Musique française*, in which the central argument hinges on the notion that both French and Italian music had developed sufficiently distinct and established standards—of style, practice, and repertoire—to allow for meaningful comparison.⁹⁶ His defence of Lully's operas as the “primary treasure” of the French stage illustrates just how entrenched Lully's works had become in the national canon. It necessarily implies that even their less “elevated” or stylistically “impure” moments were not only accepted, but embraced as integral to that legacy.

The hybridity of Lully's work remained an easy target for satire, whether during his life or after. This satire found a particularly fruitful expression in parody—both in pamphlet literature and on rival stages. As competition between theatres intensified following the creation

⁹⁵Lola Salem, “Emplois and casting at the Académie Royale de Musique: Female Opera Singers and their Roles from 1669 to 1715”, Ph.D. dissertation, University of Oxford, 2022, esp. pp. 187–208, 290; see also Noiray, “The Practical and Symbolic Functions of l'ancienne musique at the Paris Opéra before Gluck”, in *The Oxford Handbook of Operatic Canon* (Oxford University Press, 2020); Robert J Arnold, *Musical Debate and Political Culture in France, 1700–1830* (Boydell, 2017); William Weber, “La musique ancienne in the Waning of the Ancien Régime”, *The Journal of Modern History* 56, no. 1 (1984), pp. 58–88.

⁹⁶Jean-Louis Le Cerf de La Viéville, *Comparaison de la Musique italienne et de la Musique française* (Brussels, 1705–6), vol. I, p. 98: “I still agree that Lully's operas are still the primary treasure of our Theatre. It is good not to play *Amadis de Grèce* immediately after *Amadis de Gaule*, & we should not perform too often new operas to the audience so as to not age those of Lully too much. I even think that nowadays too many people have the brazenness to compose new ones.” (“Je demeure d'accord que les opéras de Lully font la principale richesse de notre Théâtre. Il est bon de ne point jouer *Amadis de Grèce* immédiatement après *Amadis de Gaule*, & on ne doit donner au public des opéras nouveaux, que de peur de rendre ceux de Lully trop tôt vieux, en les jouant toujours. Je trouve même que trop de gens ont aujourd'hui la hardiesse d'en composer.”)

of the ARM, opera became fair game for popular commentary leaning towards the ridicule.⁹⁷ Saint-Évremond's *Les Opéras* (c. 1676) already caricatured the genre's emotional excesses by presenting a mad young woman who could only express herself through song. This motif reappeared in *Les Fous divertissants* (1680), the first original play staged at the newly founded Comédie-Française, where quotations from Lully's *Proserpine* (1680) and *Bellérophon* (1679) were used to comic effect. A few years later, Dancourt satirised opera mania in *Angélique et Médor* (1685) and *Renaud et Armide* (1686)—both scored by Charpentier.

While these parodies challenged the cultural monopoly of Lully's operas, they also attested to their popular resonance and proved their adaptability. The Comédie-Italienne leaned heavily into parody, recasting Lullian tragic characters in farcical settings. Mezzetin (Angelo Constantini) composed mock laments, while *vaudevilles*—well-known tunes or famous operatic airs—were set to new, irreverent texts in the *commedia dell'arte* manner. Charles Rivière Dufresny's *L'Opéra de campagne* (1692) offered one of the most pointed examples, relocating the solemn world of Quinault and Lully's *Armide* to a rustic farm: Renaud's noble air, "Plus j'observe ces lieux" (II, 3), becomes a parody sung by Arlequin in praise of a roasting spit. The shift not only inverts the emotional intent but also relocates the opera's setting from magical Damascus to rural farce. Likewise, numerous airs from *Atys* and *Isis*, also became vaudeville. Their circulation across Foires, convents, and Opéra-Comique stages supports a model of musical culture where recycling, parody, and public memory shaped taste more than rigid aesthetic theories. Such transformations underscore the operatic culture's reliance on audience memory, where recognition itself became a source of humour.

In a mock version of *Persée*, the librettist and scholar Louis de Cahusac rewrote Méduse's tirade of terror as a jubilant love song. The exercise underscores the comic potential embedded within Lully's musical lines, and reveals how easily serious music could be repurposed for comic effect. Again, this intertextual practice challenged the supposed natural link between affect and melody, undermining the logic of absolute expression in *tragédie en musique* and laying bare its aesthetic conventions.

This practice continued well into the eighteenth century, as Lully's work represented sometimes up to half of the repertoire performed by the ARM's troupe every year. In 1737, for example, Denis Carolet's parody *Pierrot Cadmus*, staged at the Foire Saint-Germain, nostalgically lamented the original comic tone of *Cadmus et Hermione*. Carolet recast the hero Cadmus as "bouffon, amusant, polisson", and mocked the "froid, mélancolique" version offered in recent revivals at the Opéra. The parody adapted vaudevilles like "Cahin Caha", borrowing not only Lully's musical form but also reframing its affective charge. This reveals

⁹⁷Laura Naudeix, "Opera in France c. 1640–c. 1710", in Jacqueline Waeber (ed.), *The Cambridge Companion to Seventeenth-Century Opera* (Cambridge Companions to Music, 2022), pp. 232–3: "Eventually, such [parody] practices led to full-blown parodies that tweaked the plots of tragédies en musique staged at the Académie Royale de Musique, and, in so doing, opened the path to the genre of the opéra-comique. Following the expulsion of Italian actors from Paris in 1697, the Parisian fairs (the Foire Saint-Laurent and the Foire Saint-Germain) attempted to take their place. The Académie Royale responded by banning the use of song in works performed at such fair theatres; similarly, the Comédie Française forbade them to use speech. The fair theatres were obliged to come up with imaginative alternatives to compensate for the loss of spoken and sung dialogues: they required that the audience sing well-known operatic airs ('timbres') and vaudevilles. This type of interaction between the public and the actors was itself viewed as desirable by the Académie Royale, since its audience enjoyed singing along with the actors, especially during the *divertissements*."

how the comic potential of *tragédies en musique* was not forgotten, but remembered through distortion—reshaped in performance and in popular musical memory.

IV. Comic Turns and Tonal Shifts at the ARM after Lully (1687–1715)

Traditionally, the end of Louis XIV's reign has been tinged in people's minds with a certain gloom. The story of a king who fell out of love with the joy and perceived decadence of entertainments, perhaps under the influence of Françoise d'Aubigné (made Madame de Maintenon in 1675), Louis XIV's last lover, and her preoccupation with religion and morality, seems antagonistic with the presence of comedy on the Académie's stage. Additionally, the start of a costly war of aggression, the War of the League of Augsburg (1688–97), shifted Louis XIV's focus and priorities. However, the abundance of theatrical development related to comic registers, dance, and Italian singing practices presents a much more colourful portrait of this *fin-de-règne*.

After the death of Lully in 1687, the direction of the Académie took a different turn. Contrary to Lully, his son-in-law, Francine, did not combine all most important managerial and creative functions. The ranks of the administration grew bigger as Francine outsourced the necessary skills and connections for continuing the business. The successive owners and/or directors of the Parisian institution attempted to bring some fresh air to the programme, notably in order to better face the growing competition with other theatres such as the Fairs in Saint-Germain and in Saint-Laurent, the Comédie-Italienne (active once again between 1713 and 1716), and the Opéra-Comique (founded in 1714).

Looking at the programme from a bird-eye view, the Académie's repertoire after 1687 mingled new works (generally two or three per years), including those of composers André Campra (1660–1744), Henri Desmarest (1661–1741), Michel de La Barre (1675–1745) and Antoine Dauvergne (1713–1767), with consistent revivals of Lully's repertoire.⁹⁸ Substantial parts of the operatic material created under Lully's directorship were reused, and the custom was eventually formalised in the 1714 *Règlement* of the institution.⁹⁹ With the opening of the ARM, and the new diversity of composers who were suddenly invited to create for the troupe, the generic and structural issues of opera became once more a prominent matter, including the presence of comic elements on stage.

The *opéra-ballet* in particular made a come back. Historically, the ballet was structured as a series of brief danced episodes known as *entrées* (entrances), which, when numerous, were grouped into larger divisions called *parties*.¹⁰⁰ While some ballets were unified by a single overarching theme—as in *Le Ballet Royal de la Nuit*—most privileged variety and surprise over narrative continuity. The ballet was a collective artistic enterprise, yet one individual was typically credited with the *dessein* (design), responsible for the general subject and organisation of the plot. Musical and poetic contributions were entrusted to others. Printed programmes, akin to occasional poems celebrating patrons, provided audiences with the *dessein*, descriptions of *décors* and characters, and eventually included sung texts and verses—whether solemn

⁹⁸For librettos and overview of the repertoire, see *Recueil général des opéra, représentés par l'Académie royale de musique depuis son établissement*, 16 vols, (Paris, 1703–1745), 3-vol. facsimile ed. (Geneva, 1971).

⁹⁹“Règlement au sujet de l'Opéra. À Marly le 19 Novembre 1714”, Articles 6–8, quoted by Durey de Noinville and Travenol, *Histoire du théâtre*, pp. 127–8.

¹⁰⁰Naudeix, “Opera in France c. 1640–c. 1710”, p. 216.

or comic. These materials served an important social function, allowing audiences to follow the performance and to guess at the identities of the masked dancers. Generally speaking, the generic label of *ballet*, which was a more natural home for comic elements than the *tragédie en musique*, was still extraordinarily fluid in the late seventeenth-century, as outlined by Rebecca Harris-Warrick.¹⁰¹ This terminological vagueness could grant opera authors some freedom regarding the ways in which they aimed to combine different registers, characters, musical forms, sub-plots, and other musical and poetic elements.¹⁰²

The principles underlying this structure—variety, alternation, tonal diversity—did not remain confined to dance. The *divertissements*, often praised for their lightness and novelty, exemplified a broader wind of change that began to reshape the repertoire and creative processes of the ARM after Lully's death.¹⁰³ Notably, the aesthetic ideal of *variété*, central to baroque dance, began to influence the dramatic construction of operas, the nature of the plots, and the characterisation of singing roles. Within this shifting framework, comedy gained new visibility as part of a larger movement toward structural playfulness and affective contrast.

Rebecca Harris-Warrick highlights the vitality of this shifting operatic landscape in her study of the revival of Thalie, the Muse of Comedy, across several works. One notable example is *Achille et Polixène* (1687), a *tragédie* left incomplete by Lully—who died after composing only the first act—and finished by his pupil Collasse, with a libretto by Jean Galbert de Campistron. The prologue stages a telling encounter between three Muses: Melpomène (Tragedy), Thalie (Comedy), and Terpsichore—normally associated with Dance but here reimagined as the Muse of Music. Set in “a place appropriate for staging spectacles, that could serve either tragedy or comedy”, the scene places comedy quite literally “on an equal footing with tragedy”.¹⁰⁴ But this was no neutral gesture. As Harris-Warrick notes, the symbolic confrontation between tragic and comic forms reflects a broader sense of crisis—namely, the perceived “degradation” of the ARM in the post-Lully years by many contemporaries.¹⁰⁵ The prologue's stage directions describe the setting as stripped of its former splendour, nearly ruined; the Muses, appearing without their usual retinue, lament their inability to create anything worthy of the audience's gaze.¹⁰⁶ Beneath the surface spectacle, the opera asks an urgent

¹⁰¹ Harris-Warrick, *Dance and Drama*, p. 207.

¹⁰² The period also encompassed forms of experimentation with operatic formats (including that of the *tragédie en musique*). In the immediate post-Lully period, a handful of *tragédies* presented only three acts (following the Italian practice), for example. Additionally, a few works which were designated as *tragédies* should more properly have been labelled something else: *Astrée* (1691), for example, is really a *pastorale*.

¹⁰³ Harris-Warrick, *Dance and Drama*, pp. 85, 97, 103, and 130: “The step vocabulary of baroque dance is rich and varied. Feuillet's numerous *steptables* in *Chorégraphie* show that dance was based upon a limited number of fundamental movements, each of which could be modified in many ways. [...] Variety is the rule in the composition of figures, just as it is in the choice of steps, although symmetry still reigns. [...] By the early eighteenth century dancers were beginning to specialize, although most of them still performed a variety of roles. [...] In a musical style that favors variety over predictability, characterization depends on subtle interactions among all the parameters of a piece: form, key, harmony, melody, metre, rhythm, tempo, phrase structure, texture, and orchestration. It is thus more fruitful to study individual pieces in situ than to generalise.”

¹⁰⁴ Harris-Warrick, *Dance and drama*, p. 203.

¹⁰⁵ Harris-Warrick, *Dance and Drama*, pp. 203-204

¹⁰⁶ “La tristesse règne en ces lieux,/Nous rougissons de ne pouvoir lui plaire,/Hélas! Ne saurions-nous rien faire/Digne de paraître à ses yeux?” (“Sadness reigns here, we blush at our inability to please him/Alas! Are we incapable of producing anything worthy of appearing before his eyes?”)

question: can the union of comedy, tragedy, and music still produce meaningful art?

In *Les Fêtes de Thalie* (1714), the struggle between comedy and tragedy is again explicitly represented. The authors borrow directly some key elements from the Comédie-Italienne, such as the stereotypical role of the “soubrette”.¹⁰⁷ Maupoint wrote:

It is the first opera where one could see women dressed à la mode, and characters of confidantes resembling the soubrettes of the Comédie[-Italienne]. The Public was troubled at first; however people came in crowds...

Perhaps toying with nostalgia, *Les Fêtes de Thalie*'s prologue resembles that of *Achille et Polixène*'s. The muse Melpomène vaunts her glorious record over the ARM's past repertoire: “Armide, Phaéton, Atys, Roland, Bellérophon, Thétis — these give me sovereignty over this brilliant place. Muse, withdraw!”¹⁰⁸ But Thalie replies: “My sister, one tires quickly of weeping. Does anyone ever tire of laughing?”¹⁰⁹ Apollon, then, seeking a compromise between his two muses, asks Melpomène: “Could you not get together with Thalie in the same work, as you did in the past? This mixture still charms Italy today.”¹¹⁰

After the death of Louis XIV, Thalie continued to be used for explicitly reasserting comedy as a legitimate operatic mode at the ARM. In *Les Âges* (1718), librettist Louis Fuzelier placed his work under the inspiration of Thalie to defended the comic ballet, composed by Campra, as a valid musical form. In the printed preface, he made a pointed case for the aesthetic dignity of comic writing, claiming that “Thalie has as much right over music as Melpomène”, and rejecting the notion that opera must be governed solely by grave, pathetic sentiments.¹¹¹ Emphasising variety, dance, and light intrigue as essential to the ballet's success, Fuzelier appealed to the public rather than the court for legitimation.

Building on the early signs of this aesthetic change, Harris-Warrick delineates three major tendencies that influenced opera production on the stage of the ARM in the aftermath of Lully's death:

First, the infusion of new genres such as the opera-ballet changed the tone of the theater by increasing the number of works with light-hearted, or even comic elements. Second, the *tragédie en musique* came to exist in a state of tension between the Lullian model and the new tendencies; the *divertissements*, both in newly created works and in revivals, became crucial sites where such tensions played themselves out. Third, the amount of dancing on the stage expanded, in all genres, and the best dancers developed a fan base that came to the theater to see them perform, no matter what the work.¹¹²

¹⁰⁷Maupoint, *Bibliothèque des théâtres*, 136: “C'est le premier Opéra où l'on ait vu des femmes habillées à la Française, et des Confidentes du ton des Soubrettes de la Comédie. Le Public en fut d'abord alarmé ; cependant il y vint en foule...”

¹⁰⁸“Armide, Phaéton, Atys,/Roland, Bellérophon, et Thétis,/De ce brillant séjour me rendent souveraine./Muse, retirez-vous.”

¹⁰⁹“On est bientôt las de pleurer,/Se lasse-t-on jamais de rire ?”

¹¹⁰Ironically, as Harris-Warrick notes (*Dance and Drama*, 205), around the time of *Les Fêtes de Thalie*, a mixture of high and low registers in Venetian operas was actually refined towards a renewal of *opera seria*, with a more restricted register. Somehow, then, the Apollo depicted in the French ballet was not really up-to-date with the reality of Italian operatic practices.

¹¹¹Louis Fuzelier, *Les Âges* (1718), dedication to Her Royal Highness Madame, P. Ribou, F-Pn RES-YF-1683.

¹¹²Harris-Warrick, *Dance and Drama*, 204.

Despite the retirement of Beauchamps after 1687, the previous templates for building *divertissements* within the framework of operatic plots remained. The new genre of the *opéra ballet*, illustrated by André Campra's *L'Europe galante* (1697), put more and more the emphasis on that specific section by increasing the number of instrumental dances and elaborate *ariettes*. This richer form of *divertissement* "allowed the dancing body to become a site for humour, via characters borrowed from the *commedia dell'arte*" by colouring French dance styles (less athletic than their Italian counterparts) with a clear comic accent.¹¹³

With comic responsibility increasingly delegated to choreographic gesture in *divertissements*, women gain greater visibility than before. Mademoiselle Dimanche *cadette* performed the silent role of the Gypsy (Bohémienne) in *L'Estime (Les Amours déguisés, Bourgeois and Fuzelier, 1713)*; Mademoiselle Sallé appeared in lyrical roles such as Léonore, a slave to the Venetian Doctor in *La Sérénade vénitienne (Fragments de M. Lully, 1702)*, and as Atalanta in *La Tragédie (Les Muses, Campra and Danchet, 28 October 1703)*. The latter role combines dancing and singing, likely crafted to showcase the talents of young dancer-singer and balance the otherwise serious tone of the *entrée*. Much later, in *Les Fêtes d'Hébé* (third and final *entrée*, "La Danse," Rameau and Montdorge, 1747), another silent lead role of Eglé was given to the talented Mademoiselle Camargo.

Furthermore, Italian themes and symbols made a triumphant come back in Paris. Many operas became partly or wholly inspired by Venice, and in particular the Venetian Carnival and variations on the symbolic reference to masks and masquerades. It constituted at times the general landscape of different narratives and was sometimes even reflected in the presence of specific characters explicitly originating from the Italian city.¹¹⁴ This is visible not only with Campra's *L'Europe galante* (1697, 1706, 1715, 1724) but also *Le Carnaval de Venise* (1699) and *Le Carnaval et la Folie* (1704, 1719) by Destouches; the *Fragments*, a potpourri series led by Campra (1702, 1708, 1711, 1722); and other thoroughly comic works by the same composer including *Les Fêtes Vénitienes* (Campra, 1710) and *Les Fêtes de Thalie* (1714, 1715, 1722) which, despite some criticism, generated an immense success.¹¹⁵ Borrowing from previous practices, the final *entrée* of *Le Triomphe des arts* (La Barre et La Motte, 1700) features a virtuoso Italian aria, "Un dolce canto", performed by the Élisabeth Daneret Gherardi (1676–a. 1702).¹¹⁶

¹¹³Rebecca Harris-Warrick, "Dance and ballet", in Jacqueline Waeber (ed.), *The Cambridge Companion to Seventeenth-Century Opera*, Cambridge Companions to Music, 2022, p. 187.

¹¹⁴Barbara Nestola (*L'air italien*, 2020) has meticulously demonstrated in her analysis of the circulation and performance of the Italian aria in Paris at the end of the seventeenth century how much Venetian material (either original or retouched) was circulating in various spheres, including that of the Opéra.

¹¹⁵See Don Fader, "The 'Cabale Du Dauphin', Campra, and Italian Comedy: The Courtly Politics of French Musical Patronage around 1700", *Music & Letters* 86, no. 3 (2005): pp. 380–413; and Benoît Dratwicky, "Campra, Chantre Du Comique à l'Académie Royale de Musique ?", in *Le Carnaval de Venise*, CD Booklet (Glossa, 2011).

¹¹⁶Élisabeth Daneret, also known as Gherardi (variously Babet-la-chanteuse, Dancret, Daneret, Gherardy), was a singing actress active between 1676 and after 1702. She married the Italian comedian Evariste (Evaristo) Gherardi—renowned for his portrayal of Arlequin and director of the Théâtre Italien until his death in 1700—with whom she had a son who later pursued a career at the Opéra-Comique. Élisabeth began her career as a singing actress at the Comédie-Italienne on 24 August 1694 and remained there until the theatre's closure in May 1697. She subsequently joined the troupe of the Académie Royale de Musique (ARM), where she is listed in the librettos for the 1699 revivals of *Proserpine* (Lully), both as a chorister and in small roles. Her final appearance was in July 1701, singing in the chorus for the premiere of *Aréthuse* (Campra), after which she left the institution. See

The cross-dressing tradition for comic old women perduced. In the 1702 and 1708 *Fragments*, Nérine is described as an “old Venetian” advising the young Léonore, played by *haute-contre* Jean Boutelou. It reappeared in *Les Fêtes vénitiennes* by Campra and Danchet, played by Boutelou’s successors: the *taille* Jean-Louis Mantiennne (b. 1677–1739) in 1710, 1712, and 1713; the *taille* Louis-Antoine Cuvillier (1701–a. 1753) in 1731; and the *haute-contre* François-Denis Tribout (b. 1695–1761) in a variation of the ballet, *Le Jaloux trompé* (1731). Two equivalent roles also feature the same cast of *taille* or *taille*-adjacent singers for performing the same type of comedy: Bélise, mother of Léonore in *Les fêtes ou le Triomphe de Thalie*’s 1st entrée “The Daughter” (Mouret), is premiered in 1714 by Mantiennne; and Artémise in *Les Âges*’ 1st entrée “La jeunesse ou l’Amour ingénu” (Campra) premiered in 1718 by the *haute-contre* Muraire (b. 1690–a. 1752).

Although slightly outside the chronological scope of this study, the successful ballet *Les Âges* deserves attention. In the 1st entrée, already mentioned, the comic effect hinges on a general game of disguise: everyone pretends to be someone else. Most notably, Léandre disguises himself as Artémise, Florise’s governess, in an attempt to seduce the young woman. In a reversal, the old governess also assumes Léandre’s appearance in order to dissuade Florise from her love for him. The character of Artémise thus becomes a site of multiple layers of disguise—not only within the plot, but also through the casting choice (Muraire). The result is a comic *mise en abyme*, as the role accumulates internal and external cross-dressing effects. The entrée ends by a telling moral line: “Masques are most sincere” (scene 6) is announced by an anonymous Masque, performed by Mademoiselle La Garde (b. 1695–ca. 1756), in a self-aware celebration of comic artifice and its courtly audience. The sequence is framed musically by two minuets, a gavotte, and a danced *air des masques*, featuring the nasal tone of oboes and bassoon. A second aria from the same Masque follows, reflecting on the allure and dangers of female beauty. This piece includes vocal virtuosity—octave leaps, a lively triple rhythm, and ornamented reprises—before the entire entrée concludes with a rousing *air des matelots* and two branles. The integration of irony, disguise, and stylised musical variety contributes to an aesthetic of *variété* that defines the comic mode of this period.

From a broader angle, the creative impulse found in *opéras-ballets* came to contaminate the rest of the repertoire in various ways. That was true from their structure (especially in the context of ballets in which plots from each *entrée* theoretically worked in an independent manner from one another) and the level of registers (i.e. tragic, comic, light-hearted) to the number of characters and the diversity of their profiles. Whatever the operatic genre used, the margin for the authors’ creativity was thin with regard to plot structures and *topoi*. Generally speaking, poems untiringly addressed the same issue of love, fulfilled and deceived, disrupted and restored. However, variations on that theme were enabled by the incorporation of a greater number of roles, whilst subtle differences in terms of ethos allowed for actual variety on stage, depending on the performer’s age, social functions, origins, attractiveness, and so on. The amount of characters in opera plots, whether singing or dancing, increased in parallel to the multiplication of operatic works and, within ballets, of *entrées*.

Émile Campardon, *Les Comédiens du roi de la troupe italienne* (Paris: Berger-Levrault, 1880), t. 1, pp. 241–2; and Barbara Nestola, “Italian Music, French Singers. Reception and Performance Practice on the Parisian Stage at the Beginning of the Eighteenth Century”, Damien Colas and Alessandro Di Profio (dir.), *D’une scène à l’autre, l’opéra italien en Europe* (Mardaga: Wavre, 2009), t. 1, pp. 253–67.

A particularly illustrative example of this experimental dynamic can be found in *Vénus et Adonis* (1697), a *tragédie en musique* composed by Henri Desmarest on a libretto by Jean-Baptiste Rousseau, under the direct creative supervision of Jean-Nicolas de Francine. Eager to appeal to a younger, novelty-seeking audience while preserving the prestige of the Lullian model, Francine instructed Rousseau to emulate the style of Lully and Quinault's greatest operas. Indeed, the work contains clear echoes of *Atys* and *Armide*, with formal gestures such as the invocation of allegories (Jealousy for *Vénus et Adonis*, Hatred for *Armide*) and a tragic conclusion. Yet it also signals a shift in tone, moving toward a more variegated emotional and dramaturgical palette. Desmarest's music brings out subtle gradations of character and affect through vivid contrasts between vocal roles—above all in the figures of *Vénus* and *Cydippe*, respectively premiered by Marie Le Rochois and Marie-Louise Desmatins. These two women, who mirror each other in vocal range and dramatic force, channel both the heroic and the pathetic traditions. *Cydippe*, marked from the outset as a tender, self-questioning princess, is given a lament shaped by delicate intervals and rhythmic stability (Act I, scene 1), well suited to Desmatins's expressive *grand dessus*. *Vénus*, by contrast, enters (Act I, scene 4) with agile recitative lines shaped by rapid motion and abrupt intervallic leaps, signalling both vocal virtuosity and a restless emotional state. The scoring appears explicitly tailored to the vocal idiosyncrasies of Le Rochois, underscoring again the post-Lullian trend toward roles being custom-moulded to performer profiles. More than that, the dynamic between these two women—at once rivals, coquettes, and tragic protagonists—introduces an unstable register of irony, desire, and cruelty that resists generic fixity.

The effort to open the ARM's doors to a broader range of composers was accompanied by a parallel decision to expand the troupe's pool of performers. The number of male and female singers at the ARM grew steadily in the decades following Lully's death. However, this growth was not merely an additive expansion of the troupe. The overall recomposition of the ARM's troupe underwent subtler and significant transformations.

While some older performers retired or departed—many of whom had been recruited under Lully—the new wave of recruits introduced a strikingly heterogeneous group of artists. Some of these singers would remain at the Opéra for decades, such as Marie-Catherine Poussin née Tissart (1680–1767), Françoise Desjardins (b. 1685–a. 1732), Françoise Journet (1675–1719/20), Mlle Demerville (b. 1685–a. 1716), Jeanne-Marguerite Aubert (b. 1683–a. 1723), and Marie-Catherine Dulaurier (b. 1693–a. 1717)—the last four having entered the troupe simultaneously in 1705. Others, by contrast, had shorter tenures of between three and six years: Françoise-Jacquette Salley née Houry (b. 1674–1745), Mlle Bataille (b. 1685–a. 1705), and Anne-Marguerite Cochereau née Bazin de Chenvrigny (1679–ca. 1712), all hired in 1702, as well as Mlle Armand (b. 1685–a. 1708) and Mlle Vincent (b. 1687–a. 1722), hired in 1703. Despite this influx of talent, only one among these singers—Françoise Journet—attained the prestigious rank of *premier sujet*. The rest were largely confined to minor roles or understudy positions. Notably, some were cast in comic parts, highlighting once more the continuity of comedic functions within the operatic hierarchy. Rather than being marginal, these comic roles persisted as an integral and recognisable register within the post-Lullian repertoire, subtly shaping both casting practices and audience expectations.

Alongside that notable trajectory of Françoise Journet, the careers of Marie-Catherine Poussin, Mlle Dupeyré, Mlle Armand, Françoise Desjardins, and Jeanne-Marguerite Aubert—respectively recruited in 1699, 1700, 1703 (for both Armand and Desjardins), and 1705—offer

further insight into post-Lullian casting practices at the ARM. Each of these singers took on a substantial number of important secondary roles, typically drawn from the same typological categories: confidantes, allegorical figures, and lesser deities—characters that, while not central, played significant dramaturgical functions. In effect, these women competed for a similar pool of roles. Yet strikingly, their performance histories reveal little actual overlap: with few exceptions, each developed a distinct repertoire within the same structural type.¹¹⁷

The most consistent parallel appears between Armand and Poussin.¹¹⁸ Armand's progression within the troupe, however, seems to have been hampered by shortcomings in her stagecraft. As the historians Claude and François Parfaict remarked, she had "little hope to ever become a passable actress," indicating that her vocal and physical appeal was insufficient to compensate for weaker dramatic skills.¹¹⁹ Poussin, by contrast, managed to carve a niche for herself by occasionally taking on more prominent roles, including those of gentle lovers in tragedies such as Créuse (*Médée*) and Hésione (*Hésione*). Described as "tall, pretty, well-made, and blond", she stood out within the cohort of secondary women.¹²⁰ In many respects, Poussin seemed a credible candidate to inherit the vocal legacy of Marie Le Rochois's successor, Marie-Madeleine Moreau. Indeed, Poussin took on five roles previously associated with Moreau—all originally premiered by the older singer. By contrast, although Journet absorbed six roles from Moreau's repertoire, only half had been premiered by her, suggesting a looser artistic continuity. However, despite Poussin's affinity with leading repertory, she remained largely confined to secondary parts—and, notably, to what the Parfaict brothers termed "comic" roles.¹²¹ The label likely served as shorthand for ballet-derived parts or those informed by the Italian tradition, as in *Les Fêtes vénitiennes* and *Les Fêtes de Thalie*—operas where comedy, dance, and spectacle blended with recognisably foreign aesthetic codes.

¹¹⁷Overlaps in terms of repertoire between Poussin, Dupeyré, Desjardins and Aubert were rare: Poussin and Dupeyré shared Thestylis in *Alcide*, Dupeyré and Desjardins both played the roles of La Fée Principale and Logistille in *Roland*, Aubert and Dupeyré performed the same anonymous roles of Une Bergère and Une Nymphé in *Tancredé*, and Aubert and Poussin played Flore in *Atys*. Additionally, Aubert and Poussin played alongside (i.e. in the same performance) the same minor, anonymous roles of Une Calydonienne and Une Dryade (in *Méléagre*), and Une Suivante d'Urgande (in *Amadis de Gaule*).

¹¹⁸Both perform the following roles at different dates: La Gloire in *Armide* (in 1703 for Armand, in 1713 and 1714 for Poussin), Scylla in *Acis et Galatée* (1704 for Armand, 1718 for Poussin), Electre in *Iphigénie en Tauride* (in 1704 for Armand, in 1719 and 1720 for Poussin), Une Nymphé représentant Syrinx in *Isis* (1704 for Armand, 1717 for Poussin), Thémire in *Roland* (1705 for Armand, 1709 for Poussin). Like Poussin, Armand performed the role of Clorinde in *Tancredé*, a part associated with the opera's initial success. She alternated in this role with Françoise Journet in 1707, suggesting her brief alignment with more visible positions in the troupe. Earlier in her career, Armand had performed alongside Mlle Vincent and Mlle Bataille—for instance, as Charite in *Cadmus et Hermione* (1703).

¹¹⁹Claude and François Parfaict, *Dictionnaire des théâtres de Paris, contenant toutes les pièces qui ont été représentées jusqu'à présent sur les différents théâtres français et sur celui de l'Académie royale de musique* (Paris: Lambert, 1756), t. I, 302: "Mlle Armand was young and pretty, her loss was rather regretted: she had a very graceful voice, but little hope to ever become a passable Actress" ("Mlle Armand était jeune & jolie, sa perte fut assez regrettée: elle avait la voix très gracieuse, mais peu d'espérance de devenir jamais passable Actrice.")

¹²⁰Parfaict, *Histoire de l'Académie*, t. I, p. 113: "Elle a été grande, jolie, bien faite et blonde."

¹²¹Idem: "[Poussin] fut chargée ensuite des second roles et des comiques dont elle s'acquitta avec réputation."

Conclusion

Authors owed a great part of their failure or success to their ability to select and shape their performers. But just as crucial was their capacity to bind these performers to their creative vision, ensuring their artistic investments could be sustained over time. This dynamic of mutual dependency, complicated by administrative constraints, shaped casting choices at every level of the Académie Royale de Musique. From the very beginning, the ARM was marked by strategic tensions between institutional interests and the competing musical bodies that fed its repertoire and personnel. Casting decisions were frequently shaped less by a fixed system of poetic genres than by the interplay between available talents, performance histories, and emerging stylistic trends.

Comedy, in this context, was not a genre to be theorised from above, but a live and localised matter of casting, delivery, and theatrical effect. By the turn of the eighteenth century, the comic register had become a fertile ground for innovation. Lighter operas, comic ballets, and hybridised *divertissements* were not mere entertainments, but complex vehicles for vocal variety, choreographic invention, and narrative experimentation. Singers like Poussin, Armand, and Journet carved out nuanced careers through their repeated performances in roles marked by wit, irony, and dramatic agility—qualities that resisted rigid typologies. At the same time, choreographed roles and mute characters such as Atalante or the Bohémienne enabled dancers like Mlle Sallé or Mlle Camargo to embody theatrical presence beyond the spoken or sung word.

Even when the comic appeared at times to operate on the margins of the *tragédie en musique*, its force as a performative and aesthetic tool was central to the ARM's ability to adapt, respond, and survive. Through parody, dance, disguise, and character multiplicity, comedy infiltrated even the most canonical works, offering artistic structure as well as entertainment. What emerges, then, is not a story of comic exception but of comic continuity: a current running beneath the tragic mask, reshaping the stage from behind the scenes. In this light, the presence of the comic at the ARM was not only a question of taste, but a matter of operatic identity.